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Postdocs at the University of Münster

Work Situation, Job Satisfaction
and Career Development

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List of Abbreviations

AR	Akademischer Rat / Akademische Rätin (<i>lecturer</i>)
BerIHG	Berliner Hochschulgesetz (<i>Berlin Higher Education Act</i>)
BuWiK (formerly BuWiN)	Bundesbericht Wissenschaftlerinnen und Wissenschaftler in einer frühen Karrierephase (<i>National Report on Early Career Researchers</i>); before 2025 it was called 'Bundesbericht Wissenschaftlicher Nachwuchs' (<i>National Report on Junior Scholars</i>)
CERes	Münster Centre for Emerging Researchers
DAAD	Deutscher Akademischer Austauschdienst (German Academic Exchange Service)
DFG	Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (<i>German Research Foundation</i>)
DZHW	Deutsches Zentrum für Hochschul- und Wissenschaftsforschung (<i>German Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies</i>)
InWiDeHo	Internationale Wissenschaftler*innen an deutschen Hochschulen (<i>International Academics at German Universities</i>)
2. JPS	2. Jenaer Postdoc-Studie (<i>2nd Jena Postdoc Study</i>)
KOAB	Kooperationsprojekt Absolventenstudien (<i>Graduate Study Cooperation Project</i>)
LfbA	Lehrkraft für besondere Aufgaben (<i>university instructor with high teaching load</i>)
LVV	Lehrverpflichtungsverordnung (<i>Teaching Obligation Regulations</i>)
nacaps	National Academics Panel Study
NHG	Niedersächsisches Hochschulgesetz (<i>Lower Saxony Higher Education Act</i>)
PNM	Postdoc Network Münster
R1/R2 Researcher	First Stage/Recognised Researcher (EU phase model)
UKM	Universitätsklinikum Münster (<i>University Hospital Münster</i>)
UM	Universität Münster (<i>University of Münster</i>)
UniKoN	UniWiND-Koordinierungsstelle Nachwuchsinformationen (<i>UniWiND coordination office for early-career information</i>)
UniWinD (formerly UniWiND)	Universitätsverband zur Qualifizierung von Wissenschaftler*innen in frühen Karrierephasen in Deutschland (<i>German University Association for the Qualification of Early-Career Researchers in Germany</i>); before 2025, it was called 'Universitätsverband zur Qualifizierung des wissenschaftlichen Nachwuchses in Deutschland' (UniWiND)
WissZeitVG	Wissenschaftszeitvertragsgesetz (<i>German Academic Fixed-Term Contract Act</i>)

1 Introduction

Postdocs develop their own research areas, write grant applications, teach, supervise undergraduates, master's students, and doctoral researchers. They contribute to the academic discourse through conference presentations, publications and reviews. They also organise conferences, manage projects and work on committees. Thus, the portfolio of tasks for postdocs is highly diverse. This brings greater autonomy and more responsibility than researchers experience during the doctoral phase. Nevertheless, the findings from the 2025 German Federal Report on Early-Career Researchers (BuWiK, 2025), the 2023 Nature Postdoc Survey and other relevant studies present a mixed picture about the reality of postdoc life.

On the one hand, postdocs are in a relatively privileged economic position: unemployment is low at 1–2 %, they are more likely to hold a leadership position than people without a doctorate, and even the “chances of a professorial appointment seem to be rising slowly” (“Chancen auf eine Berufung scheinen [...] langsam zu steigen”; translation by R. M.; BuWiK, 2025, p. 156). With the success of the tenure-track model for junior professorships, postdocs – female postdocs in particular – now have better access to the professorial career track (BuWiK, 2025, p. 243). However, a temporary W1 professorship does not guarantee a permanent professorship and the so-called leaky pipeline¹ continues to persist (BuWiK, 2025, p. 32). On the other hand, the working conditions associated with the postdoc phase remain unsatisfactory, even burdensome, for many early career researchers. Thus, the DZHW (*German Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies*) Science Survey 2023 found that “71 % of postdocs on fixed-term contracts are considering leaving the academic system. In addition to the high workload, the insufficient career prospects resulting from the German Academic Fixed-Term Contract Act (WissZeitVG) plays an important role in those considerations” (“71 Prozent der befristet arbeitenden Postdocs einen Ausstieg [aus dem Wissenschaftssystem erwägen, R. M.]. Neben der hohen Arbeitsbelastung spielen auch unzureichende berufliche Perspektiven im Zusammenhang mit dem Wissenschaftszeitvertragsgesetz (WissZeitVG) eine wichtige Rolle.”; translation by the authors; Fabian, Heger & Fedzin, 2024, p. 5). According to the DAAD and DZHW's InWiDeHo study, international postdocs often experience a lack of clarity about career options in the German academic system, in addition to a lack of suitable language courses, which is particularly problematic given that the need for German as a foreign language represents “one of the greatest hurdles” for this group (“eine der größten Hürden”; translation by R. M.; InWiDeHo, 2023, p. 9).

Although the data on postdocs has improved steadily over the past ten years, in particular, through the studies mentioned above, Germany still lacks long-term, systematic data collection for this target group. For example, this is the case with the Cooperative Graduate Studies Project (KOAB) and the National Academics Panel Study (nacaps). Indeed, the varied and inconsistent definition of the term *postdoc* (see Chapter 3.1) itself is a key challenge making it difficult to compare data and reach the target group.

¹ This term describes the phenomenon whereby the proportion of women working in academia decreases as qualifications and career stage increase (“Je fortgeschrittener die Qualifizierungs- und Karrierestufe, desto geringer ist der Anteil der in der Wissenschaft tätigen Frauen.”; translated by R. M.; BuWiK, 2025, p. 32).

As the University of Münster's central academic graduate support centre, the Münster Centre for Emerging Researchers (CERes) is interested in understanding who our postdocs are and what they need from our interdisciplinary graduate support services. Therefore, the CERes postdoc survey pursued two main goals:

1. To gather information on postdocs' needs and expectations regarding career planning and skills training, in order to shape and further develop CERes structures and services for postdocs accordingly.
2. To expand the database on the situation and satisfaction of postdocs at the University of Münster, in relation to their current postdoctoral study.

In spring 2024, we initiated a standardised written online survey to investigate these questions. The survey was conducted from late November 2024 to mid-February 2025. The results of our subsequent analyses are presented below. These findings are not only of interest to postdocs, support structures and decision-makers at the University of Münster, as they also provide research managers, university officials and early career researchers with broader insight into the needs and concerns of postdocs and how they can be monitored meaningfully.

2 Key Results

The analysis presented in the key findings of the CERes postdoc report is primarily based on participants' responses to our survey and, in part, on personnel statistics from the University of Münster (UM) and the University Hospital Münster (UKM). However, as the survey was voluntary, the results are not statistically representative. Nevertheless, the findings from the following group comparisons and correlation analyses still provide valuable insight, even if the groups being compared are not proportionately represented in the sample as they are in the personnel sample.

2.1 Sample

- In total, **1,434 staff members** at the University of Münster, including in the Faculty of Medicine and University Hospital Münster, **hold a doctorate** (without a habilitation or professorship). The personnel statistics discussed below are based on the dataset for this personnel sample.
- **A total of 214 respondents participated in the CERes postdoc survey.** The effective participation rate is therefore 15 % of eligible personnel, or 17 % excluding the Faculty of Medicine. Of the 214 respondents, 114 were identified as postdocs* according to the narrower definition used herein and are referred to below as postdocs* or the postdoc* sub-group.²

² The criteria used for this definition are explained in Chapter 3.1.

- **Around one fifth** of survey respondents are **internationals** as defined herein.³
- **Female postdocs are slightly overrepresented in our samples.** They account for 56 % of survey respondents and 49 % of the personnel sample.
- At around 47 %, **respondents from the natural sciences are clearly overrepresented in the survey sample.** In comparison, only around 29 % of the personnel sample are working in the natural sciences.
- **81 % of respondents stated that they were the first person in their family of origin to obtain a doctoral degree.** A further 42 % said that they were also the first person in their family of origin to obtain a higher education degree.
- For almost **two thirds of the University of Münster personnel sample, it has been more than six years since they completed their doctorate;** among respondents, that figure is 45 %.
- **The proportion of the personnel sample who are fixed-term employees at the University of Münster is around 58 %, which is significantly below the national average.** In 2022, this stood at around 81 % for doctorate holders in Germany under the age of 45 (BuWiK, 2025, Table B14). Among our survey respondents, 75 % reported being employed on fixed-term contracts.
- **Around three quarters of the University of Münster personnel sample are funded by the University (through internal budgets or *Haushaltsmittel*) and around one quarter by third-party funds.** Furthermore, UM postdoc personnel in the humanities and social sciences are more likely to be funded by the University than by third-party funds than those in the natural and life sciences.

2.2 Diversity Dimensions

- While the proportion of all UM postdoctoral employees on fixed-term contracts between the sexes shows little difference, **female respondents to this study (81 %) are significantly more often on a fixed-term contract than male respondents (65 %).**
- **The relationship between fixed-term contracts and academic discipline within the group of respondents is the opposite of that in the personnel sample:** while around 60 % of the UM postdoc personnel in the humanities, social sciences and natural sciences are on fixed-term contracts, the figure is around 75 % in the life sciences. For the respondent sample, 62 % of those from the life sciences stated that they were employed on fixed-term contracts. While among the respondents from both the humanities and social sciences and the natural sciences, the figure was around three-quarters.

³ In this report, international respondents are defined as those who spent most of their primary and secondary schooling outside Germany. For a more detailed explanation, see Chapter 3.5.

- Although among our survey respondents, there are slightly more men with caring responsibilities than women (56 % versus 54 %), **women are much more likely to report spending more than 15 hours per week on childcare or other care duties.** This is also reflected in contracted working hours among respondents: **31 % of female respondents and 13 % of male respondents said they worked part-time.**
- **International respondents spend more time on research activities and are also more satisfied with this share of their time than non-international respondents.** However, the international respondents' need for training opportunities, such as language courses and an introduction to the German academic system, is considerably greater than that of the non-international respondents.

2.3 Satisfaction and Occupational Stress Experience

- **57 % of the survey respondents ($n = 122$) are rather or very satisfied with their current working situation.** Overall, social satisfaction is rated more highly than occupational satisfaction. Specifically, the statement "I experience the cooperation with my direct colleagues as successful." received the highest level of agreement ($M = 3.28$). By contrast, the item "I have a lot of contact with researchers in a similar career phase." showed the lowest level of agreement ($M = 2.72$). In relation to their satisfaction with general working conditions, the degree of independence is rated highest, and the *WissZeitVG (Wissenschaftszeitvertragsgesetz, which translates to German Academic Fixed-Term Contract Act)* lowest. **Overall, within the survey sample, occupational satisfaction is rated notably lower among fixed-term employees than among those in permanent positions.**
- **Dissatisfaction with structural conditions and restrictive aspects of academic freedom may, in part, be compensated for by positive factors** (see analysis of free-text fields in Chapter 5). These include, in particular, the experience of meaningful work, good social relationships, recognition from others, and the opportunity to carry out research and teaching independently. However, if these conditions are impaired, for example through conflict with superiors or colleagues, the situation is experienced as significantly more burdensome.
- **Slightly more than one third of the postdocs surveyed feel excessively burdened by their workload at least once a week.** Fixed-term employees report excessive stress more frequently than those with permanent contracts. In addition, the experience of stress is more pronounced among full-time employees than among part-time employees. **Thus, the group most affected by occupational stress is fixed-term full-time staff.**
- The frequency of excessive occupational stress has a direct impact on overall satisfaction. **Respondents who feel burdened more often report lower overall job satisfaction than those who feel burdened less often.**
- In a free-text question, participants were asked which services and contact points the University of Münster offers staff coping with strain. **In almost half of the cases ($n = 36$), respondents**

could not name any contact point. None of the 14 English-language respondents could identify a specific service.

- 93 % of respondents said that they talk about occupational stress with people in their private circle, while 83 % reported discussing it with colleagues. **Only one third of respondents said they also speak to their supervisors about their burdens.**

2.4 Career Development

- **Around one third of respondents ($n = 31$) rate their knowledge of the German academic system as rather poor or poor,** while 59 % ($n = 101$) also consider their knowledge of academic systems in other countries insufficient.
- Almost two thirds of respondents stated that they had spent all stages of their education (school, undergraduate study, doctorate and previous postdoctoral positions) predominantly in Germany. Prior to their postdoc position at the University of Münster, **40 % of respondents completed their doctorate at the University of Münster, and 29 % of respondents completed their doctorate *and* (in part) their undergraduate studies there as well.** The University of Münster, therefore, appears to be a permanently attractive location for many researchers, although no comparative figures from other universities are available at this time.
- **Respondents who had not previously studied or worked at the University of Münster, prior to commencing their current postdoc position, were more likely to report pursuing goals aimed at a long-term academic career.**
- Around 85 % of respondents reported wanting to further develop their qualifications in their current field of work. At the same time, the respondents rated career prospects outside academia more positively than their prospects within academia. **Furthermore, respondents from the social sciences and humanities are more strongly inclined towards professorial career goals than natural scientists.**
- **Around 45 % of respondents reported talking about their own career planning in their professional environment at most once per semester.**
- Among the **training opportunities most frequently rated as helpful are support with third-party funding applications, individual career coaching, leadership training and project management.** Individual career coaching is rated as particularly beneficial by women. Around 90 % of female respondents said that this measure has helped or would help them reach their long-term postdoctoral career goals. Among male respondents, around 62 % agreed that such services would be or have been helpful.

3 Methodology

After defining the target group of postdocs more precisely in Chapter 3.1 for the purposes of this study, Subchapters 3.2–3.5 outline the conduct of the CERes Postdoc Survey and describe the survey instrument, methodology, and sample.

3.1 Definition of the Target Group

Defining the group of postdocs immediately raises several challenges. First, the definition varies by country or region and by discipline. Second, some definitional criteria, such as seeking a further qualification or greater degree of independence, are rarely reflected in personnel statistics, which makes targeted outreach difficult. As Linda Jauch and colleagues summarise in a UniWiND (*German University Association for the Qualification of Early-Career Researchers in Germany*) publication on prospects for postdocs, “Everyone knows who is meant by the term postdoc – but almost everyone means something different” (“Jeder weiß, wen er oder sie damit [mit dem Begriff *Postdoc*, R. M.] meint – nur meint fast jede:r etwas Anderes”; translation by R. M.; Jauch, Bart & Herberger, 2023, pp. 9–10). This poses a challenge in addition to the previously discussed insufficient evidence for the situation of postdocs in Germany. One familiar, and to an extent, internationally recognised definition for the term is based on the EU phase model from 2011. In a framework paper, the European Commission distinguishes between four academic career phases (European Commission, 2011, p. 2): *R1 First Stage Researcher* (up to the point of PhD), *R2 Recognised Researcher* (PhD holders or equivalent who are not yet fully independent), *R3 Established Researcher* (researchers who have developed a level of independence) and *R4 Leading Researcher* (researchers leading their research area or field). Depending on their individual situation, postdocs are classified as R2 or R3 researchers. While this distinction appears substantively useful and offers guidance while remaining adaptable, the qualification criteria are, in part, still vague. As a result of these broad definitions, it is difficult to collect data on criteria, such as the degree of independence, in a form that is suitable for statistical analysis. Overall, the definition we have of “postdocs” is fragmented with blurry boundaries or, as the title of a much-cited paper by the former UniWiND coordination office for early-career information (UniKoN) from 2021 put it, they are the “Dr Unknown” (“Dr. Unbekannt”; translation by R. M.).

At the University of Münster, there is likewise no generally accepted definition of the target group, hence the central personnel databases do not assign individuals to a *postdoc* category. In analogy to the 2nd Jena Postdoc Study (Kauhaus, Franzmann & Krause, 2018, p. 17), our questionnaire was addressed to all employees and researchers at the University of Münster who hold a doctoral degree, except those employed as junior professors, junior research group leaders or professors, in order to obtain an initial dataset that was as broad as possible.⁴ Nevertheless, eight participants classified themselves as a junior research group leader or junior professor. This

⁴ On the questionnaire cover page and in the survey announcement, it was stated specifically: “The questionnaire is addressed at all postdocs who are currently working/conducting research at the University of Münster (incl. UKM). In order to participate, it is **not** required that you strive for a career in academia”

broad approach also meant that people took part who, according to common definitions, do not belong, in the narrower sense, to the postdoc target group. This includes research managers employed as academic staff and permanently employed staff with a high teaching load. However, based on the survey responses, a sub-sample corresponding to a narrower definition of postdoc was identified from among the survey respondents (for the criteria used, see Table 3.1). This sub-sample is referred to herein as postdocs* or the postdoc* sub-group. All statistical calculations were carried out both for the overall postdoc sample, that is all survey responses ($n = 214$), and for the postdoc* sub-group ($n = 114$). Any noteworthy differences are reported accordingly. Otherwise, it can be assumed that there are no substantial differences between the samples.

Table 3.1: Terminology and criteria for referring to the target group

Terms used in the report	Criteria
Total population, personnel sample ($N = 1,434$)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - completed doctorate - no habilitation, junior research group leadership or (junior) professorship - registered as an employee in the UM or UKM personnel database
Postdocs, postdoctoral researchers, survey participants, respondents ($n = 214$)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - completed doctorate - no professorship - research active at the UM, including the Faculty of Medicine or UKM⁵
Postdocs*, postdoc* sub-group ($n = 114$)	<p>All criteria listed above for postdocs and either</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) in fixed-term employment and within 6 years of completing their doctorate, b) in fixed-term employment, over 6 years have passed since they completed their doctorate and they are pursuing a career goal in research⁶, or c) permanently employed but pursuing a further career goal in research (such as a professorship)

⁵ The survey was also addressed to postdocs without an employment relationship with the University of Münster, such as scholarship holders and visiting researchers.

⁶ A career goal in this context is considered academic if in item 5 of category 4 (career planning and prospects), the person indicated that within the next five years they plan to achieve at least one of the following goals: “complete my habilitation”, “meet the qualification criteria for a professorship”, “become a junior research group leader”, “be appointed to a junior professorship (with/without tenure track)”, “be appointed to a permanent professorship”.

3.2 Conduct of the Survey

The survey was conducted as an anonymous online survey using *LimeSurvey* at the University of Münster between November 2024 and February 2025. The questionnaire was available in German and English. In line with the target group defined in Chapter 3.1, all academic staff at the University of Münster (UM) holding a doctorate, including those at the Faculty of Medicine and University Hospital Münster (UKM), were contacted by mass email at the end of November 2024 and again with a reminder email at the end of January 2025. In total, 2,113 individuals were invited to respond, of whom 1,100 were affiliated with the Faculty of Medicine or UKM.⁷ However, this method was unlikely to reach the (international) doctorate holders conducting research at the UM on a scholarship. For this reason, the following additional channels were used to disseminate the survey: following the university's poster distribution system and advertising displays, posters were placed at central locations in both printed and digital form, and flyers were placed or distributed at events attended by the target group. In the first mass-mail phase, members of the CERes scientific advisory board and other central university units were also contacted and asked to forward the survey link via their protocols. The survey was also promoted through the Postdoc Network Münster (PNM), which engages primarily with international postdocs. Finally, in the second mass-mail phase, the dean's offices of the 15 faculties were contacted and asked to forward the survey to the target group. Throughout the survey period, the survey was also promoted on the CERes website. However, the questionnaire links were not published on the website in order to minimise non-target group participation.

The data submitted was collected anonymously, without timestamps, and without IP addresses. Submitted responses were stored on an internal university server to which only CERes staff and system administrators had access. In addition, the data was aggregated for descriptive and inferential statistical analyses in such a way that no conclusions could be drawn about individuals. At the start of the questionnaire, respondents were also informed that participation was voluntary and that they could discontinue the survey at any time without penalty, and that any question could be skipped or the "no answer" option selected.

3.3 Survey Instrument

The questionnaire was first drafted in German and then translated into English. The 2nd Jena Postdoc Study (2nd JPS, 2018), the 2021 National Report on Junior Scholars (BuWiN, 2021), the 2022 PostdocNet survey of the Max Planck Society, and the 2023 Nature Postdoc Survey provided inspiration for item development. The questionnaire was designed at CERes and optimised and finalised through several feedback rounds with different stakeholders: from the outset, the target group itself was involved in the design through the PNM board. The CERes scientific advisory board and selected central units of the University of Münster (including Academic Controlling, data protection officers, research funding support, the International Office

⁷ The number of people from University Hospital Münster is so high because the dataset mistakenly also included individuals who were no longer employed.

and the Diversity Officer) were also sent the draft questionnaire and asked to provide feedback. Finally, the questionnaire was reviewed by the Rectorate, tested by six postdocs in both languages, and finally programmed with the support of a student assistant.

The questionnaire includes items in the following five categories: (1) academic vita and work situation, (2) demographics, (3) job satisfaction and occupational stress experience, (4) career planning and prospects, and (5) training needs and offers. The first three categories were used to gather information on the composition of the target group and their situation. Categories 4 and 5 provide CERes, as an overarching graduate centre, with insight into what postdocs need and how they can be best supported. As more than 10 minutes were needed to answer the questions, even after shortening the questionnaire, participants were shown either category 3 (job satisfaction and professional strain) or category 4 (career planning and prospects) at random. After the last regular question, participants could decide whether they wanted to end the survey or complete the additional category that had not been shown at the outset. Around 74 % of respondents provided the additional information. The full questionnaire is attached to this report in the Appendix.

3.4 Analytical Methods

The aim of this analysis is, first, to provide a descriptive account of the participants' current situation. For categorical variables, frequencies were calculated and presented in tabular and/or graphical form. For metric variables, both means (M) and standard deviations (SD) are reported. In addition, inferential statistical group comparisons were carried out for various variables. The main categorical variables (independent variables) were gender (female/male), internationality (yes/no), research discipline (humanities and social sciences/natural sciences/life sciences), contract status (fixed-term/permanent) and employment status (full-time/part-time). For categorical variables, chi-square tests were calculated. For metric variables, t-tests were used to compare two groups, and one-way analyses of variance were used to compare more than two groups. Tukey tests were used for post-hoc comparisons. Finally, two-way analyses of variance were calculated for individual variables (see, for example, Chapter 4.3 on time use as a function of position type and research discipline). The focus here was on examining interactions between the two respective factors. Further analyses considering more than two factors simultaneously were not pursued because of the strongly uneven and sometimes small cell sizes. All inferential statistical analyses were conducted at a significance level of $\alpha = .05$. Appropriate measures of effect size are reported to assist with interpretation. To illustrate the findings, both group means and standard deviations are reported.

3.5 Sample Description

The questionnaire cover page was accessed 609 times in total (501 times in German and 108 times in English). In 316 cases, at least the first question category was completed (269 via the German questionnaire and 47 via the English questionnaire). During data cleaning, two test

runs and all cases in which neither of the two random categories 3 or 4 had been completed were removed. This left 187 cases in the German-language dataset and 27 cases in the English-language dataset, giving a sample size of $n = 214$. If the number of persons in the personnel sample is taken as the total population ($N = 1,434$), the response rate is around 15 %.⁸ For the postdoc* sub-group, which is comprised of those respondents who meet the narrower definition of postdoc*, only the responses which meet the criteria in Table 3.1 were considered. A total of 114 cases can be assigned to the postdoc* sub-group, of whom 87 completed the German questionnaire and 27 the English questionnaire. Unfortunately, a corresponding postdoc* population size cannot be identified based on the personnel statistics because the relevant data, for example, career goal, is not routinely collected by the University (cf. Kauhaus et al., 2018, p. 21). In the present dataset, however, the postdoc* subgroup within the personnel sample is likely to be much smaller than the personnel sample overall.

Of the survey participants, 56 % identified as female (59 % among postdocs*).⁹ Age was collected in four bands (< 30 years, 30–35 years, 36–40 years and > 40 years). While only 3.8 % of respondents were under 30 at the time of the survey, 58.5 % were between 30 and 40 years old, and 37.6 % over 40. In comparison, the postdoc* sub-group is, as expected, younger: 6.2 % were under 30 at the time of the survey, 69.9 % were between 30 and 40, and 23.9 % were over 40.

Subject affiliation was not collected according to the University of Münster's 15 faculties, but instead using the higher-level categories of the DFG (*German Research Foundation*) subject classification system (humanities and social sciences, life sciences, natural sciences and engineering – engineering, for example, is not represented by a separate faculty at the University of Münster). The intention behind this was to avoid being able to identify individuals within smaller academic units through combinations of personal characteristics. An overview of the distribution of participants by research discipline is provided in Table 3.2. Both among all respondents and among postdocs*, the largest group belongs to the natural sciences (around 47 % in each case).

⁸ If the employees of the University Hospital Münster who were contacted, which included medical staff with a doctorate, are excluded from the personnel sample, the total population drops to $N = 1,063$, and the response rate increases to around 17 %.

⁹ In addition to “female” and “male”, the response options “diverse”, “other”, “none” and “no answer” were available for the gender question. However, less than 5 people selected “no answer”, so these were treated as missing values.

Table 3.2: Distribution of respondents by research discipline

Research discipline	Total population (Personnel sample)		Respondents		Postdoc* sub-group	
	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%
Humanities and social sciences	448	31.2	76	35.7	41	36.0
Natural sciences (incl. engineering)	408	28.5	99	46.5	54	47.3
Life sciences	371	25.9	37	17.4	18	15.8
Other	207	14.4	/	/	/	/

Note: Percentages are based on the number of valid cases in each category.

The time passed since completion of the doctorate, based on the date of the viva, was also collected in bands (< 1 year, 1–3 years, 4–6 years, > 6 years). 45.2 % of respondents said they had completed their doctorate more than six years ago (see Table 3.3). Even among postdocs*, around one third (32.4 %) fall into this category. However, half of the postdoc* sub-group reported having completed their doctorate 1–3 years ago.

Table 3.3: Distribution of respondents by time passed since completion of doctorate

Time since completion of the doctorate	Total population (Personnel sample)		Respondents		Postdoc* sub-group	
	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%
< 1 year	15	1.1	18	8.6	16	14.0
1–3 years	264	18.4	59	28.1	57	50.0
4–6 years	248	17.3	38	18.1	2	1.8
> 6 years	897	62.6	95	45.2	39	34.2

Note: Percentages are based on the number of valid cases in each category.

In comparison, the spread of these characteristics in the University of Münster personnel statistics¹⁰ is as follows: the gender ratio is almost balanced, with women accounting for 49.2 %. Women are, thus, overrepresented among the respondents (56 %). There is also a clear difference in relation to age. Within the personnel sample, 47 % are between 30 and 40 years old, and around 49 % are over 40 years old. The survey participants are, thus, relatively young, which may be explained by the fact that the personnel sample also includes people who do not belong to the survey target group. Looking at the research discipline, it is noticeable that natural scientists are clearly overrepresented among our respondents, as they account for 46.5 % of respondents but only 28.5 % of the personnel sample. The fact that the proportion of people from the life sciences is lower among the respondents than in the personnel sample (17.4 % compared with 25.9 %) is likely due to the fact that the personnel statistics include medical staff who do not carry out research alongside patient care. The already high proportion of survey participants whose doctorate was completed more than six years ago (around 45 %) is even higher in the total population at around 63 %. The likely reason for this is that the personnel statistics include all employees with a doctorate, regardless of whether they are working towards a further academic qualification.

Internationality has been measured differently across various studies. For example, the 2nd JPS (Kauhaus et al., 2018) makes the distinction based on whether the higher education entrance qualification was obtained in Germany, within the EU or beyond the EU. In contrast, the PostdocNet survey determined internationality based on the respondents' stated country of origin, while the Nature Postdoc Survey determined internationality based on the country in which the respondents currently lived. Moreover, drawing on higher education personnel statistics for these figures, BuWiK 2025 defines internationality by nationality. For CERes, a graduate support service, country of origin and nationality are less relevant. Rather, for target-group-oriented qualification measures, it is more important to know how much of a postdoc's education (school, undergraduate study, doctorate and previous postdoctoral positions) was undertaken in Germany, elsewhere in Europe and beyond Europe, and which language skills they have. Therefore, our definition of internationality is closest to that of the 2nd JPS (Kauhaus et al., 2018), and this study designates postdocs as international when most of their primary and secondary schooling was undertaken outside Germany. This applies to 45 cases, i.e., 21 % of respondents. Among the postdocs*, there are 27 internationals, which corresponds to 23.7 %.

In addition to the standard demographic information, respondents were also asked to indicate how strongly they identify with various professional terms (see Table 3.4). Inspired by the 2nd JPS (Kauhaus et al., 2018), this item reflects higher-education policy debates on the definition of postdoc (UniKoN 2021) and the appropriate designation of postdoctoral researchers by asking

¹⁰ The records of all employees with a completed doctorate but without a professorship, junior professorship or junior research group leadership were identified and included in the personnel sample. To achieve this, the data from the University Hospital Münster and the Faculty of Medicine had to be merged with the data from the other faculties. The dataset from the Faculty of Medicine is from August 2025. However, the data therein for the year the doctorate was completed use 1 December 2025 as the reference date and therefore does not reflect the exact status at the time of the survey. For the other faculties, the dataset is from 15 February 2025.

the target group about their own preferences. By far the most strongly endorsed term is *scientist/researcher* (or, in German, *Wissenschaftler*in*). Just as in the 2nd JPS (Kauhaus et al., 2018, p. 98), around 86 % of respondents to the CERes postdoc survey identify with this designation either rather strongly or very strongly. In addition, 67 % of respondents identify with the term *postdoc* or *postdoctoral researcher* rather strongly or very strongly. As expected, this proportion is slightly higher among the postdoc* sub-group at 71 %. It is nevertheless striking that among our postdocs*, 29 % identify rather little or not at all with this term.

Table 3.4: Identification with terminology

Term	Respondents		Postdoc* sub-group	
	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%
Researcher	175	85.8	94	85.5
Postdoc / postdoctoral researcher	134	66.7	78	70.9
Discipline-specific title, e.g., biologist, lawyer, etc.	145	75.5	73	68.9
<i>Nachwuchswissenschaftler*in</i> (specific German term for <i>junior academic</i>)	74	38.0	43	39.5
Early Career Researcher	56	28.3	37	33.6
Emerging Researcher	42	21.8	29	26.9

Note: Only cases in which respondents identified rather strongly or very strongly with the respective term were taken into account. Percentages are based on the number of valid cases in each category.

Further patterns emerge when this identification with terminology is combined with time since completion of the doctorate (see Fig. 3.1). The proportion of those who identify rather strongly with the terms *postdoc* and *early-career researcher* is highest among respondents whose doctorate was completed 1–3 years ago (the term *postdoc* = 84.5 % and *early-career researcher* = 55 %). Moreover, identification with the term *scientist/researcher* and with discipline-specific titles is reported as rather strong, in particular, by respondents whose doctorate was completed 4–6 years ago or more than 6 years ago (*scientist/researcher* = 90 % and *discipline-specific title* = 81 %).

Fig. 3.1: Identification with terminology in relation to time since completion of doctorate (in %)

Note: Percentages refer to the proportion of respondents within a time category who identify rather strongly or very strongly with the respective term. Percentages are based on the number of valid cases in each category.

4 Academic Vita and Work Situation

One aim of the CERes postdoc survey is to learn more about the postdocs employed at the University of Münster so that these findings can, when appropriate, be incorporated into advisory and training services. Therefore, educational background (see Chapter 4.1) is an essential aspect that reflects how closely rooted respondents are at the University of Münster and highlights a diversity that has attracted increasing attention, particularly since the founding of the non-profit association *Erste Generation Promotion – EGP e. V.* (First-Generation Academics). By comparing the employment conditions described in Chapter 4.2 with data from BuWiK 2025 and the 2nd JPS (Kauhaus et al., 2018), the respondents' working situation can be placed in a wider context. The distribution of activities shown in Chapter 4.3, in turn, provides insight into the day-to-day working life of our participants at the University of Münster.

4.1 Educational Biography

First, the analysis of educational pathways reveals that the majority of respondents (62 %) were predominantly in Germany during all stages of their education (see Fig. 4.1). Second, it is striking that more than one third of respondents (40 %) completed their doctorate at the University of Münster immediately before taking up their postdoc position, and that 29 % had also studied

there as undergraduates, at least temporarily (see Fig. 4.2). Among the postdoc* sub-group, the educational pathway distribution is similar both in terms of the country perspective and the university perspective.¹¹ The only group of respondents that stands out includes those who did not move to the University of Münster directly after completing their doctorate but at a later point in time: they account for 21 % of all respondents and 39 % of the postdocs*.

Fig. 4.1: Educational pathway – country perspective (in %)

Note: Respondents were asked to tick in a matrix where they had spent most of each stage of their education (school, undergraduate study, doctorate and previous postdoctoral positions). The options were: in Germany, in another European country, or in a country outside Europe. Percentages are based on the number of valid cases in each category ($n = 214$).

¹¹ Distribution within the **postdoc* sub-group** ($n = 114$) for the **country-based comparison**: school through to postdoc phase predominantly in Germany: 61 %; doctorate and/or postdoc phases predominantly in Germany: 18.4 %; other: 12.3 %; postdoc phase predominantly not in Germany: 7.9 %; school, college/undergraduate, doctorate and postdoc phases predominantly not in Germany: 2.6 %.

Distribution within the **postdoc* sub-group** ($n = 108$) for the **university-based comparison**: studies, doctorate and subsequent postdoc at the University of Münster: 32.4 %; postdoc at the University of Münster directly after the doctorate: 25.9 %; not directly after the doctorate at the University of Münster: 38.9 %; other: 12 %; doctorate and subsequent postdoc at the University of Münster: 8.3 %.

Fig. 4.2: Educational pathway – university perspective (in %)

Note: Respondents were asked to tick in a yes/no matrix indicating which stages of their academic qualification (undergraduate studies, doctorate, postdoc directly after the doctorate) they had completed at the University of Münster. Percentages are based on the number of valid cases in each category ($n = 201$).

To gain a better understanding of the educational backgrounds of the target group, the study also looked at the respondents' social environment. Six statements described the academic qualifications of relatives and people in the respondents' close private environment, and participants were asked to indicate whether each statement applied to them. Fig. 4.3 shows that although almost one third of respondents (30 %) knew some people with an academic career before starting their doctorate, a clear majority stated that they were the first person with a doctorate in their family of origin (81 %) or extended family of origin (69 %). Whether having contacts within academic circles or with individuals with academic careers was helpful for respondents' own qualifications or career planning remains unclear. However, following Pierre Bourdieu's concept of *social capital*¹², it can be assumed that access to academic networks or relationships with people in academic careers provides resources that facilitate careers in academia and support positioning within the academic system. For the design of cross-disciplinary qualification and guidance, this result clearly indicates that system knowledge and informal rules need to be made

¹² In short, Bourdieu defines social capital as "resources that are based on membership in a group", from which members of that group benefit both materially and symbolically ("Ressourcen, die auf der Zugehörigkeit zu einer Gruppe beruhen"; quote translated by R. M.; Bourdieu, 1983, pp. 190–191, 192).

transparent and that an academic *habitus*¹³ in the sense used by Pierre Bourdieu should not be taken for granted among postdocs.

Fig. 4.3: Academic experience in the social environment

Note: Respondents were asked to tick in a yes/no matrix which scenarios applied to their educational biography. Family of origin = parents, siblings. Extended family of origin = grandparents, aunts, uncles, cousins. Percentages are based on the number of valid cases in each category.

4.2 Employment Conditions

The respondents' employment conditions provide information about the circumstances under which postdocs at the University of Münster are attempting to advance their research, teaching and careers. In addition, findings on the proportion of fixed-term staff, funding or care work can be meaningfully compared to data from other studies. This offers guidance for both the target group and university decision-makers.

As in the overall scientific and artistic staff at German universities (BuWiK, 2025, Fig. B26), the largest group in this study's respondent sample is also, by far, non-professorial academic staff or *Wissenschaftliche Mitarbeitende* (75 %; see Table 4.1 Table 4.2). In the 2nd JPS (Kauhaus et al., 2018), this group accounted for 85 % (p. 26). In the personnel statistics of the University of

¹³ In Bourdieu's work, the concept of habitus is "exclusively related to social actors" ("ausschließlich auf soziale Akteure bezogen"; quote translated by R. M.; Rehbein & Saalman, 2014, p. 111). Bourdieu understands habitus as "a system of internalised patterns [...], which enable a person to generate all the typical thoughts, perceptions, and actions of a culture – and only these" ("ein System verinnerlichter Muster [...], die es erlauben, alle typischen Gedanken, Wahrnehmungen und Handlungen einer Kultur zu erzeugen – und nur diese"; quote translated by R. M.; Bourdieu, 1970, p. 143).

Münster (excluding University Hospital), the proportion of non-professorial academic staff is actually slightly higher, around 91 %. However, this group also includes academic civil servants, who in the CERes postdoc survey probably selected the option “other”. The fact that the proportion of fixed-term contracts is higher among postdocs* than in the overall sample of respondents (83 % versus 74 %) is to be expected given the employment models still common in German higher education. However, at 57.8 %, the proportion of fixed-term employees at the University of Münster is significantly lower than the national average, which was around 81 % in 2022 for doctorate holders under 45 in higher education personnel statistics (BuWiK, 2025, Table B14).¹⁴ Among respondents to the CERes postdoc survey, 75 % said they were employed on fixed-term contracts. In the 2nd JPS (Kauhaus et al., 2018), the figure was 78 %. Here too, it is likely that the difference is partly explained by the broader target group covered by the personnel statistics.

BuWiK 2025 also shows that among researchers holding a doctoral degree (excluding junior research group leaders and professors), the proportion on fixed-term contracts falls with age and career stage. Specifically, while 90 % of doctorate holders under 40 are on fixed-term contracts, the figure for those aged 40 to under 45 is 62 % (BuWiK, 2025, Table B14). A similar pattern is visible among staff at the University of Münster, although the proportion of respondents on fixed-term contracts decreases as age increases: of those under 40, 80.7 % are fixed-term, while only 37.7 % of respondents over 40 are on fixed-term contracts. In the CERes postdoc survey sample, 89 % of employees up to the age of 40 and 51 % of employees over 40 are on fixed-term contracts. It should be considered, however, “that analogous to the decline in the proportion of fixed-term contracts with increasing age, the absolute size of the age groups also decreases” (“dass – analog zur Abnahme der Befristungsanteile mit zunehmendem Alter – auch die absoluten Größen der Altersklassen abnehmen”; translation by R. M.; BuWiK, 2025, p. 190). Therefore, one plausible interpretation, also suggested in BuWiK 2025 (p. 190), is that fixed-term employees leave universities as their age and length of service increase, while permanently employed staff tend to remain in the system.

Turning to gender, there is hardly any difference among the fixed-term employees in the University of Münster personnel sample, similar to the national average (see BuWiK, 2025, p. 190): 58.7 % of female and 56.8 % of male staff have a fixed-term contract. However, among our respondents, there are clear differences: at 81 %, the proportion of fixed-term contracts among female respondents is significantly higher than among male respondents (65 %). The higher average age of male respondents may be an influencing factor here. For example, 34 % of the women surveyed are over 40, compared with 42 % of the men.

Differences in fixed-term employment also appear across research disciplines. While in the personnel statistics, 58.8 % of employees in the natural sciences and 57.8 % in the humanities and social sciences are on fixed-term contracts. This proportion is markedly higher in the life sciences (73 %). In the survey sample, the pattern is exactly the opposite: around 78 % of

¹⁴ The figure of 81 % is obtained when the categories “R2 – doctorate holders under 40” and “R2 – doctorate holders from 40 to under 45” (see Table B14) are combined. It should be noted here that the CERes postdoc survey sample may also include people over 45, since the response option > 40 years does not impose an upper limit.

respondents in the natural sciences and around 75 % in the humanities and social sciences reported being on fixed-term contracts, whereas only 62 % of respondents from the life sciences did so. One possible explanation is again the age distribution: participants from the life sciences have a higher proportion of respondents over 40 (51 % compared with 32 % of respondents in the natural sciences and 39 % in the humanities and social sciences).

Table 4.1: Employment conditions

Characteristic		Total population (Personnel sample)		Respondents		Postdoc* sub-group	
		N	%	n	%	n	%
Position/title	Non-professorial academic staff	966	90.87	159	74.6	92	80.7
	Junior research group leader or junior professorship			8	3.8	3	2.6
	Other (e.g., LfbA, AR)	97	9.13	46	21.6	19	16.7
Fixed-term contract	Yes	829	57.81	156	73.6	94	82.5
	No	605	42.19	56	26.4	20	17.5
Employment status	Part-time position	386	26.92	49	23.2	23	20.2
	Full-time position	1048	73.08	161	76.3	91	79.8
Teaching obligation	Yes			119	57.8	63	57.3
	No			87	42.2	47	42.7
Funding type	University budget	1051	73.29	123	57.5	65	57.0
	Third-party funding	364	25.38	89	41.6	49	43.0
	Other (e.g., scholarship)	19	1.32	11	5.6	5	4.4

Note: Percentages are based on the number of valid cases in each category.

As far as employment status (full-time/part-time) is concerned, staff at the University of Münster are much less likely to hold a part-time position (27 %) when compared with the national average (48 %) (BuWiK, 2025, p. 136). There is also a difference related to gender. While at the federal level, according to BuWiK 2025, 57 % of female and 41 % of male academic and artistic staff under 45 (excluding professors) work part-time, among the University of Münster personnel sample, the corresponding figures are 33.4 % of women and 16.3 % of men. Among respondents, the distribution is similar, although the categories are not directly comparable because our survey data identifies participants as over or under 40 years of age.

More than half of the survey participants (58 %) said that their employment contract included a teaching obligation. As most respondents are employed as academic staff on fixed-term full-time contracts, it is unsurprising that the majority of respondents with teaching duties have a teaching load of less than five hours per week during the semester (31 %), and only 18 % report

a teaching obligation of between five and ten hours per week.¹⁵ Notably, around 17 % of respondents teach although they are not contractually obliged. A further 11 % of respondents do not teach but would like to. Interest in further involvement in university teaching may be related to the fact that teaching experience is expected on academic CVs and it provides the opportunity to test one's teaching skills and motivation for teaching.

More than half of the survey respondents (58 %) reported that their position is funded by the university, while 42 % are funded by a third party. 8 % of respondents reported being funded by more than one source. In the University of Münster personnel sample, the difference is much larger: around 73 % of doctorate-holding staff are funded with university funds and about 25 % with third-party funds. The distribution of funding type across research disciplines shows, both for the personnel sample and the survey respondents, that doctorate holders in the humanities and social sciences are more likely than those working in the other two research disciplines to be funded by the university rather than a third party (see Tables Table 4.2 and Table 4.3). There is a similar difference in funding type for researchers in the humanities and social sciences compared to those in the natural and life sciences in the 2nd JPS (Kauhaus et al., 2018, p. 29). Among the CERes survey respondents, it is also notable that 17 participants selected multiple funding types and 10 participants answered "I don't know" or gave no answer for this question. Gender-based differences in funding type are minimal in the personnel sample: approximately 73 % of female and 73 % of male staff holding a doctorate are funded by the university, and around 25 % of both males and females are funded by a third party. The survey respondents ($n = 202$) deviate slightly from this: men are slightly more likely to be funded by the university (55 % versus 50 %) and, correspondingly, women are slightly more likely to be funded by a third party (39 % versus 33 %).

Table 4.2: Funding type (personnel sample)

Funding type	Humanities and social sciences		Life sciences		Natural sciences	
	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%
University budget	348	77.7	251	67.7	290	71.1
Third-party funding	100	22.3	107	28.8	118	28.9
Other	0	0	13	3.5	0	0

Note: Percentages are based on the number of valid cases in each category.

¹⁵ According to the teaching obligation regulations of the state of North Rhine-Westphalia (LVV), the teaching obligation for fixed-term academic staff is four hours of instruction per week ("4 Lehrveranstaltungsstunden") (cf. § 3(4)).

Table 4.3: Funding type (survey respondents)

Funding type	Humanities and social sciences		Life sciences		Natural sciences	
	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%
University budget	48	64.0	16	47.1	43	45.3
Third-party funding	19	25.3	14	41.2	40	42.1
Other	8	10.7	4	11.8	12	12.6

Note: Percentages are based on the number of valid cases in each category.

Beyond work-related employment conditions, private commitments can also affect the work situation. Participants were therefore asked how much time they spend on average per week on childcare and/or other care work, side jobs or self-employment, and voluntary work or political engagement. Of the respondents, 117 people (around 58 %) said they were engaged in voluntary work, with 71 % spending less than five hours per week on it. Fifty-one people (around 26 % of respondents) reported a side job or self-employment, and again, 71 % reported spending less than five hours per week on this. In relation to care work, 111 people (55 %) reported a weekly time commitment that, for 60 % of these 111 respondents, amounted to more than 15 hours per week. Examining this item by gender is particularly revealing. While the proportions of men (56 %) and women (54 %) engaged in care work are very similar, many more women reported spending more than 15 hours per week on childcare and/or care duties (see Figs Fig. 4.4 and Fig. 4.5). It is, therefore, not surprising that significantly more women (31 %) than men (13 %) said they worked part-time. BuWiK 2025, using data from the DZHW Science Survey 2023, clearly shows that the proportion of fathers within the academic community becomes markedly higher when compared with that of mothers as career stage advances. According to BuWiK 2025, while among doctoral researchers, only slightly more women than men report having children (18 % versus 16 %), this reverses among postdocs, and there are slightly more male than female (56 % versus 52 %) postdocs with children. This gap then widens further, and among professors, 76 % of parents surveyed are male and 59 % female (BuWiK, 2025, Fig. B81).

Fig. 4.4: Other commitments by gender (in %)

Note: Percentages are based on the number of valid cases in each category.

Fig. 4.5: Time spent on care work by gender (in %)

Note: Percentages are based on the number of valid cases in each category.

4.3 Distribution of Time Across Work-Related Activities

In order to better understand the work situation of postdocs, it is also useful to consider the proportion of time spent on various work activities. In the 2nd JPS (Kauhaus et al., 2018, pp. 35–38), the time spent on core activities during the lecture period and outside the lecture period was measured by asking respondents to distribute time shares using sliders. This same basic design was adopted for this item in the CERes postdoc study, and participants were asked to indicate the time distribution for various activities in percentages. However, instead of using sliders, numerical input fields were used in which respondents could enter percentages between 0 and 100. We also added an additional activity area: professional training.

As in the 2nd JPS (Kauhaus et al., 2018), it is also evident among postdocs at the University of Münster that research takes up the largest share of working time both in and between lecture periods, followed by teaching and administrative tasks (see Figs. Fig. 4.6 and Fig. 4.7). The difference between time allocation in and between lecture periods is also similar to that of the respondents from Jena, where during lecture-free periods, i.e., between semesters, the share of time for research rises (from 35.4 % to 45.6 %), while the share for teaching falls (from 23.9 % to 13.2 %). The remaining activity areas remain almost unchanged. This distribution is roughly in line with the values from the 2nd JPS (Kauhaus et al., 2018): there, postdocs spent 38 % of their weekly working time on their own research and 22 % on teaching. During lecture-free periods, this ratio was reversed: 13 % of time was spent on teaching and 47 % on research activities (see 2nd JPS, Kauhaus et al., 2018, p. 35). In addition, the University of Münster survey respondents estimated spending around 4 % of their working time on further professional training.

Fig. 4.6: Time spent per activity area **during** the lecture period

Note: Percentage of time. The percentages are calculated using the mean value for valid cases in each category ($n = 214$).

Fig. 4.7: Time spent per activity area **outside** lecture period

Note: Percentage of time. The percentages are calculated using the mean value for valid cases in each category ($n = 214$).

Further group comparisons were conducted based on the time shares for research and teaching. First, the respective values for semester time and the lecture-free periods between semesters were averaged. Based on these values, mean comparisons were performed according to position type (fixed-term vs permanent), internationality (international vs non-international) and research discipline (humanities and social sciences vs life sciences vs natural sciences). Since considering all three variables at the same time would produce some combinations with minimal case numbers, two two-way analyses of variance were calculated instead: one for each of the two dependent variables (model 1: position type and internationality and model 2: position type and research discipline). The same analyses were also carried out for these variables in relation to how appropriate the time invested in research and teaching was perceived to be.

Regarding the proportion of time spent on **research**, there is no significant difference between research disciplines ($F(194, 2) = 1.31$, n. s.). However, in addition to a significant difference ($F(194, 1) = 8.92$, $p = .003$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.13$) in how much time is spent on research between respondents in fixed-term positions ($M = 45.43$, $SD = 25.24$, $n = 149$) and respondents in permanent positions ($M = 29.40$, $SD = 26.03$, $n = 51$), the amount of time spent on research differs according to contract duration (fixed-term or permanent) and research discipline ($F(194, 2) = 2.71$, $p = .069$, partial $\eta^2 = .027$), as shown in Fig. Fig. 4.8. Not only do the survey respondents in permanent positions in the humanities and social sciences ($M = 20.74$, $SD = 14.01$, $n = 19$) spend less than half as much time on research as their colleagues in fixed-term positions ($M = 44.57$, $SD = 25.17$, $n = 57$), the discrepancy among respondents in the life sciences is of a

similar magnitude (permanent: $M = 40.42$, $SD = 28.10$, $n = 12$; fixed-term: $M = 38.14$, $SD = 24.58$, $n = 21$).

Fig. 4.8: Share (in %) of weekly working time spent on **research** by contract type and **scientific discipline**

Note: Group means. The percentages are calculated using the mean value for valid cases in each category ($n = 200$).

When asked whether enough time is spent on research, assessments differ significantly between research disciplines ($F(188, 2) = 8.97$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .105$). Respondents in the natural sciences experience the time invested in research as fairly appropriate ($M = -0.55$, $SD = 0.97$, $n = 91$), while in the humanities and social sciences, and in the life sciences, the time invested is perceived as clearly too low (humanities and social sciences: $M = -1.16$, $SD = 0.82$, $n = 69$; life sciences: $M = -1.18$, $SD = 0.87$, $n = 34$). In contrast, differences according to contract type are not significant ($F(188, 1) = 0.22$, n. s.), although markedly different time shares were reported depending on contract duration (fixed-term/permanent).

A further analysis shows that the time share devoted to research is significantly higher among our international respondents ($F(200, 1) = 17.74$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .081$) than among their non-international colleagues (international: $M = 53.45$, $SD = 25.78$, $n = 43$; non-international: $M = 38.29$, $SD = 25.38$, $n = 161$). Fig. 4.9 shows that the difference is particularly striking in permanent positions (international: $M = 57.72$, $SD = 32.74$, $n = 9$; non-international: $M = 23.95$, $SD = 20.26$, $n = 43$). However, the small number of cases here calls for cautious interpretation.

Fig. 4.9: Share (in %) of weekly working time spent on **research** by contract type and **internationality**.

Note: Group means. The percentages are calculated using the mean value for valid cases in each category ($n = 204$).

Assessment of the time invested also differs significantly according to internationality ($F(190, 1) = 4.97, p = .027, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .025$). In line with the time shares, international respondents considered the time spent on research more appropriate than their colleagues, who rated the share as “rather too low” (international: $M = -0.62, SD = 1.08, n = 42$; non-international: $M = -0.95, SD = 0.90, n = 152$).

As expected, the time share for **teaching** is significantly higher among our respondents in permanent positions ($F(190, 1) = 12.21, p < .001, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .060$) than among their colleagues on fixed-term contracts (permanent: $M = 25.84, SD = 21.26, n = 49$; fixed-term: $M = 16.24, SD = 14.62, n = 147$). Moreover, respondents in the humanities and social sciences are particularly heavily involved in teaching, significantly more so than respondents in the other two disciplinary groups ($F(190, 2) = 14.24, p < .001, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .130$). Looking at combinations of characteristics, the respondents who are permanently employed staff in the humanities and social sciences stand out in particular. With an average share of around 40 % of weekly working time spent on teaching ($M = 40.28, SD = 20.70, n = 18$), this group is clearly teaching more than all other subgroups. The level of these time shares is also reflected in the number of teaching hours per week during the semester. The group most likely to have a teaching load of more than 10 teaching hours per week during the semester is, by far, respondents from the humanities and social sciences (63.6 %). In the natural sciences, the figure is 27.3 %, and in the life sciences, 9.1 %. However, no significant difference was found in the time spent teaching between respondents with international and non-international backgrounds.

When asked how appropriate the time invested in teaching is perceived to be, the result, in good alignment with the time shares, shows a significant difference depending on research discipline ($F(171, 2) = 6.91, p = .001, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .075$). Here too, respondents in the humanities and

social sciences stand out from those in the other disciplines. They report spending slightly too much time teaching ($M = 0.45$, $SD = 0.86$, $n = 66$), while respondents in the life sciences and natural sciences are more likely to rate the time invested as “appropriate” (life sciences: $M = -0.16$, $SD = 0.86$, $n = 31$; natural sciences: $M = 0.03$, $SD = 0.98$, $n = 80$). A question for further research that emerges here would be the extent to which other factors, such as class size and assessment formats or the way research is conducted, influence the time needed for teaching and research and the perceived appropriateness of these allocations.

5 Job Satisfaction and Occupational Stress Experience

Perceived stress and satisfaction in the postdoc phase are two important aspects for understanding the situation of R2 and R3 researchers more clearly. According to the Nature Postdoc Survey 2023 ($n = 3,838$, mainly from biomedicine), overall satisfaction with the postdoc phase fell from 60 % in 2020 to 55 % (Nordling, 2023, pp. 419–420). Furthermore, 52 % of their respondents said they had considered leaving academia out of concern for their mental health (Nordling, 2023, p. 422). The Max Planck Society’s PostdocNet assessed postdocs’ mental health in its 2024 survey using standardised instruments. The result was that 28 % of their respondents showed signs of moderate to severe depression according to the 8-item Patient Health Questionnaire, and 25 % showed signs of moderate to severe anxiety according to the 7-item General Anxiety Disorder Scale (Russell, Davies, Skirgård, Wiegand & Samwald, 2025, p. 18).

In our CERes postdoc survey, one of the two randomly assigned question categories asked participants about their satisfaction with collaboration and networking first, and then asked them about their satisfaction with general working conditions. In the second part of this section, they were asked about their experience of work-related stress. Around two thirds of respondents (63 %) experience excessive stress rarely to, at most, once a month. Conversely, around one third (37 %) of our respondents reported feeling excessive strain at least once a week or more (see Fig. 5.1). No statistically significant difference was observed between all respondents and the postdocs* subgroup ($\chi^2(1, n = 193) = 2.27$, $p = .132$, $V = 0.11$). Nor were there any statistically notable differences in stress level within the sample related to gender, postdocs with care responsibilities, international postdocs or research discipline. Specifically, among female employees, the portion who feel excessive strain at least once a week is slightly lower than among male respondents (36 % versus 38 %). Another interesting difference appears in the comparison of the group means for fixed-term status and employment status (full-time/part-time) (see

Fig. 5.2). Fixed-term postdoctoral staff are generally more often excessively burdened than postdoctoral employees with permanent contracts, and full-time staff holding a doctorate reported feeling excessively burdened more often than part-time staff holding a doctorate. The group that reported experiencing excessive strain most frequently was the fixed-term full-time staff.

Fig. 5.1: Occupational stress experience (in %)

Note: Percentages are based on the number of valid cases in each category (n = 193).

Fig. 5.2: Excessive stress by contract type and employment status

Note: The group means are based on the number of valid cases in each category.

Most respondents (93 %) are most likely to speak about their situation with people in their private environment, such as partners, other family members or friends. While 83 % of participants also talk to colleagues about their professional strain, but only 36 % do so with their supervisors. Respondents were least likely to speak about their strain with professional contacts, such as psychotherapists (18 %), or with university advisers at the University of Münster (9 %). Eleven people said they do not talk to anybody about this issue. Of these, however, seven selected at least one other point of contact, suggesting that they do have someone to turn to in certain situations. Four people (2 %) did not select any other option for this item. The free-text responses to the question about which support services the University of Münster offers for dealing with stress were also notable. Almost half of the people who completed the question (47.4 %, $n = 36$) could not name any services. Among the 14 English-language responses, not a single person could name a specific point of contact.

The frequency of perceived excessive stress is directly linked to overall satisfaction. Respondents who feel burdened more often report lower overall job satisfaction than those who feel burdened less often (frequently burdened: $M = 2.89$, $SD = 0.75$; less frequently burdened: $M = 2.56$, $SD = 0.82$; $t(185) = 2.746$, $p = .007$, $d = .417$). Nevertheless, it can be noted that more than half of respondents (57.0 %, $n = 122$) are rather or very satisfied with their current working situation. In order to measure satisfaction in a slightly more differentiated way, as in the 2nd JPS (Kauhaus et al., 2018), various aspects of working life were investigated. In the questionnaire, these were split into two matrices, the first containing “I” statements about collaboration and networking (for example, “I experience collaboration with my direct colleagues as successful”) – hereafter referred to as “social satisfaction” – and the second addressing general working conditions (for example, “scope/length of working hours”) – hereafter referred to as “occupational satisfaction”. A four-point scale was used for both matrices: for social satisfaction, the scale ranged from “I strongly disagree” to “I fully agree”, while for occupational satisfaction it ranged from “very dissatisfied” to “very satisfied”. Comparing the means of the two sets of questions (see Table 5.1 and Table 5.2), the social satisfaction matrix shows that the statement “I experience collaboration with my direct colleagues as successful” has the highest mean ($M = 3.28$), while “I have a lot of contact with researchers at a similar career stage” has the lowest mean ($M = 2.72$). All means are still clearly above the theoretical midpoint of the scale. For occupational satisfaction, the gap between the highest and lowest means is much greater. Respondents are most satisfied with the degree of independence ($M = 3.32$). However, clear dissatisfaction is expressed with the German Fixed-Term Academic Contract Act (WissZeitVG; $M = 1.25$) and the predictability of one’s career ($M = 1.60$). A high level of satisfaction with the social working climate but low satisfaction with the predictability of one’s own career was also found among respondents in the 2nd JPS (Kauhaus et al., 2018, p. 43).

Table 5.1: Statistical comparison of social satisfaction

Item	<i>n</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	α
Overall	214	2.89	0.58	0.75
Successful collaboration with direct colleagues	191	3.28	0.75	
Appreciation of work in the workplace and academic community	191	3	0.79	
Good feedback and support from supervisor	191	2.86	1	
Good networking with researchers from other working groups	191	2.75	0.91	
Lots of contact with researchers at a similar career stage	191	2.72	0.87	
Feeling of security and trust in the social working environment	185	2.77	0.95	

Note: *n* = sample size, *M* = mean, *SD* = standard deviation, α = Cronbach's alpha.

Table 5.2: Statistical comparison of occupational satisfaction

Item	<i>n</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	α
Overall	214	2.36	0.50	0.70
Degree of independence	191	3.32	0.81	
Availability of funding for one's own research	177	2.66	0.96	
Scope/length of working hours	187	2.86	0.84	
Fixed-term duration of contract	176	1.95	1.17	
German Fixed-Term Academic Contract Act (WissZeitVG)	149	1.25	0.58	
Career advancement opportunities	181	1.93	0.80	
Opportunities for professional reorientation	161	1.96	0.77	
Predictability of career	185	1.60	0.83	
Social relationships in the work context	188	2.95	0.79	
Family-friendliness	154	2.45	1	
Time for private life	183	2.52	0.90	

Note: *n* = sample size, *M* = mean, *SD* = standard deviation, α = Cronbach's alpha.

Since the significance of individual items is limited, social satisfaction and occupational satisfaction were also analysed statistically as coherent question sets (see also Table 5.1 and Table 5.2). It stands out that respondents' social satisfaction is overall higher ($M = 2.89$, $SD = 0.58$) than their

occupational satisfaction ($M = 2.36, SD = 0.50$): the mean for overall satisfaction with the current work situation¹⁶ is 2.75. While there are no notable differences in general, social or occupational satisfaction related to gender, research discipline, full-time or part-time employment status, or age group, there are clear patterns when the group means are related to fixed-term or permanent contract duration, internationality and time since doctorate. As Fig. 5.3 shows, fixed-term employees ($M = 2.88, SD = 0.59$) have almost the same mean for social satisfaction as permanent employees ($M = 2.91, SD = 0.57$), but when occupational satisfaction is considered, it is on average somewhat lower among fixed-term employees ($M = 2.26, SD = 0.45$) than among those with permanent contracts ($M = 2.64, SD = 0.52$). Statistically, however, this effect appears only in the full respondent sample ($t(189) = -2.96, p = .003, d = -.49$), not within the postdocs* sub-group ($t(100) = -1.88, p = .063, d = -.48$).¹⁷

Fig. 5.3: Social and occupational satisfaction by contract status

Note: The group means are based on the number of valid cases in each category.

¹⁶ At the end of the question block on satisfaction, was the question, “All in all, how satisfied are you with your current working situation?” Respondents could again choose an answer on a four-point scale from “very dissatisfied” to “very satisfied”.

¹⁷ To test the statistical relation between *occupational satisfaction* and *fixed-term status*, the response item “fixed-term duration of your contract” was excluded in order to avoid associated bias.

The study participants were asked to name, in free-text fields, aspects of their work situation which they are satisfied or dissatisfied with, as well as factors that are particularly burdensome or that support their well-being. Of the 214 respondents, 162 named factors contributing to satisfaction and 147 factors contributing to dissatisfaction. In addition, 88 participants mentioned burden factors and 107 well-being factors. As part of a qualitative content analysis, which is loosely based on the methodology of Mayring (2022), an inductive category system was developed, including the following main categories: *freedom*, *meaningfulness*, *appreciation*, *collaboration* and *structures*. A detailed overview of the categorised responses can be found in the Appendix (Table 0.1). The largest and most extensive category, freedom, can be divided into time-related, spatial and content-related aspects of freedom. Flexible working hours were mentioned, in particular, as a satisfaction-enhancing condition, while uncertain prospects for the future, lack of stability and a high temporal workload led to dissatisfaction. Spatial flexibility in the form of remote-working opportunities was emphasised positively. At the same time, however, respondents were dissatisfied with the structural expectation of geographical mobility. For example, respondents with families often reported having to move or accept long commuting distances. Content-related freedom in teaching and research, for example, the opportunity to set one's own topics and priorities, was described by the respondents as satisfactory. The opportunity to submit one's own third-party funding applications and assume responsibility for one's own budget also falls within this content-structural aspect of freedom. However, this freedom is partly restricted by additional administrative tasks and by high pressure to work, apply for funding and publish.

Meaningful aspects of academic work were consistently named as satisfaction-enhancing. Two respondents even described this as the reason for continuing to work in academia:

Meine Arbeit an sich ist sehr schön. Ich mache weiter, weil ich eine große Leidenschaft für meine Arbeit habe. [My work itself is very nice. I keep going because I have a great passion for my work.]

I love science. If I would not love science I would have left years ago.

Others emphasised feeling that they are able to make a difference (“das Gefühl, etwas bewegen zu können”) or that they feel that they can support other students and doctoral researchers in their research (“Studierende und PhDs bei ihrer Forschung unterstützen und weiterhelfen”). Appreciation was also named as a central factor in satisfaction or dissatisfaction. However, as the comments show, this aspect depends strongly on the immediate working environment: some respondents reported appreciative supervisors, colleagues and academic communities, while others reported a lack of recognition from the same groups. Statements about collaboration were similarly ambivalent. While some postdocs highlighted a great team atmosphere (“tolles Teamklima”) or having a very good relationship with their supervisors, others described having a difficult working relationship with their supervisors or reported “a certain degree of unprofessionalism among team members”. A good social working environment and good relationships with colleagues were also frequently mentioned as factors that promote wellbeing.

It is also clear that structural conditions, in particular, contribute to respondents' dissatisfaction. In relation to infrastructure, respondents expressed both satisfaction (for example, with good workplace equipment and the high quality of libraries) and dissatisfaction (for example,

with the nature of the workplace, lack of support or lack of a budget for career development). Dissatisfaction with fixed-term contracts was particularly pronounced. While two people named their permanent contract as a factor contributing to satisfaction, 15 respondents expressed clear dissatisfaction about the lack of long-term prospects other than a professorship. The implications this can have for working and private life are illustrated by this comment:

*Die Unzufriedenheit mit der Arbeitssituation stammt aus der gesamten Situation der Unplanbarkeit meiner Karriere und deshalb auch meines Lebens (durch Befristung, WissZeitVG, Aufenthaltssituation). Dies wiederum hat eine sehr negative Wirkung auf die Zusammenarbeit und Vernetzung im Berufsalltag. Die meisten Nachwuchswissenschaftler mit befristeten Verträgen, mit denen man in Kontakt kommt, haben weder die Zeit noch die Kapazitäten zusammenzuarbeiten oder sich zu vernetzen. Jeder ist mit dem eigenen ‚Überleben‘ ständig beschäftigt und dementsprechend überfordert. Für Wissenschaftler*innen (alle, aber insb. Frauen) mit Familien [...] ist die Last völlig unrealistisch, was viele aus der Wissenschaft und der Uni ‚raustreibt‘. In meiner Arbeitssituation ist es für mich unvorstellbar, eine Familie zu gründen.*

[Dissatisfaction with the work situation stems from the entire situation of my career being unplannable and, therefore, also my life (because of fixed-term contracts, the WissZeitVG, and my residence situation). This, in turn, has a very negative effect on collaboration and networking in everyday professional life. Most early-career researchers on fixed-term contracts whom I am in contact with have neither the time nor the capacity to collaborate or network. Everyone is constantly occupied with their own ‘survival’ and is correspondingly overwhelmed. For researchers (all of them, but especially women) with families [...] the burden is completely unrealistic, which drives many out of academia and the university. In my working situation, it is unimaginable for me to start a family.]

From the perspective of constructive qualitative analysis (cf. Charmaz, 2006), it is also worthwhile to consider the circumstances and factors which were not named. For example, hostility towards research and researchers (DZHW, 2024) or low confidence in one’s own abilities (Krapp, 2022) were not mentioned. Similarly, topics such as unequal distribution of work, individual discrimination and bullying (Ahmad, 2025; Vallbracht, 2025) did not appear, or appeared only rarely, in the responses. In relation to this, the perspective of former postdocs who have recently left academia would be of particular interest for further analyses.

Overall, any dissatisfaction with structural conditions and freedom-restricting aspects, such as high workload, among the University of Münster postdoc survey respondents seems to be partly balanced by the experience of meaningful work, good social relationships, the appreciation experienced and the opportunity to shape research and teaching independently. However, their work becomes all the more challenging when these self-efficacy-enhancing conditions are compromised, for example, by conflict with supervisors or colleagues.

6 Career Planning and Prospects

“Only 24 % of doctorate holders work in the academic system long-term”, according to BuWiK 2025 (“Nur 24 % der Promovierten arbeiten langfristig im Wissenschaftssystem”; translated by R. M.; p. 156). The majority, specifically 62 %, leave academia immediately after their doctorate (BuWiK, 2025, p. 178). This group is also attributed advantages on the labour market that are linked to the fact “that the immediate leavers pursue particular career goals that influence both their early exit and their economic success” (“dass die Sofortausgestiegenen

besondere Karriereziele verfolgen, die sowohl den frühen Ausstieg als auch den wirtschaftlichen Erfolg beeinflussen“; translated by R. M.; BuWiK, 2025, p. 179). As already indicated in the introduction, the chances of being appointed to a professorship are indeed rising, yet on average across all disciplines, there are still 21 applications per appointment. In the 2nd JPS (Kauhaus et al., 2018), respondents were least satisfied with the predictability of their career (p. 39), and the InWiDeHo study (2023) concludes that international researchers consider opaque and unreliable career paths and language barriers as the key obstacles to long-term prospects in the German academic system (Jaudzims & Oberschelp, 2023, pp. 9–10, 61).

To gain deeper insight into the prerequisites for career planning and the concrete career goals of postdocs at the University of Münster, participants in the CERes postdoc study were asked about this topic in the other of the two randomly assigned questionnaire categories.¹⁸ The number of responses is, therefore, for some questions, considerably lower than in the non-randomised question categories.

Respondents were first asked to assess how well they knew the German academic system and academic systems in other countries. The term *academic system* was specified as the organisational structure of higher education institutions, career opportunities, qualification requirements, research culture and funding opportunities. Around one third of respondents (32 %, $n = 31$) said their knowledge of the German academic system was rather poor or poor. More than half (59 %, $n = 101$) rated their knowledge of academic systems in other countries at a similar level. As expected, there is a statistically significant association between both items and respondents' (inter-)nationality. German postdocs rated their knowledge of the German academic system more highly than international postdocs ($t(92) = 4.14, p < .001, d = .888$). Conversely, international respondents rated their knowledge of other academic systems more highly than German postdocs ($t(168) = -3.61, p < .001, d = -.653$).

Five items were analysed to assess career planning and prospects (see Table 6.1). Only the postdoc* sub-group was included here, as we can assume, with high certainty, that these individuals are still in a qualification phase. Accordingly, 85.3 % of respondents rather or fully agreed with the statement that they wanted to further qualify in their current field of work. At the same time, they rated career prospects outside academia somewhat more positively ($t(98) = 1.93, p = .056, d = 0.19$) than those within academia (within: $M = 2.56, SD = 0.98$; outside: $M = 2.31, SD = 0.91$). Just over two thirds of postdocs* (70.9 %) rather or fully agreed that they had set concrete career goals for the coming five years (item: “I know exactly what I want to achieve in the next five years.”). However, only 54.9 % of postdocs* knew what concrete steps were required to achieve these goals.

¹⁸ To further reduce the expected completion time for the questionnaire, participants were shown either category 3 (job satisfaction and occupational stress experience) or category 4 (career planning and prospects) at random at the start of the survey. At the end, they could decide whether they were willing to respond to the additional category.

Table 6.1: Career planning among the postdoc* sub-group (in %)

Item	I completely disagree.	I rather Disagree.	I rather agree.	I completely agree.	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
I know exactly what I want to achieve in the next 5 years.	8.7	20.4	46.6	24.3	2.86	0.89
I know exactly what steps I need to take to achieve my 5-year goal(s).	13.7	31.4	45.1	9.8	2.51	0.85
I intend to further qualify in my current field of work.	3.9	10.8	48.0	37.3	3.19	0.78
I view my career prospects in the academic field positively.	20.8	37.6	31.7	9.9	2.31	0.91
I view my career prospects outside the academic field positively.	13.9	37.6	26.7	21.8	2.56	0.98

Note: *n* = between 101 and 103, *M* = mean, *SD* = standard deviation

More than half of the postdoc* sub-group (54.8 %, *n* = 104) said they spoke about career planning with someone in their work environment at least once per semester or more frequently; around 42 % did so more than once per semester. However, this means that around 45 % of postdocs* speak about their own career planning in their professional environment at most once per semester.

Finally, participants were asked whether they pursued 15 possible career goals: the response options were *yes*, *maybe* and *no*. Fig. 6.1 shows that for the postdoc* sub-group, securing third-party funding, making one's own research more visible and expanding one's academic network are among the most frequently mentioned five-year goals. Research abroad, appointment to a junior professorship or non-academic career goals, in contrast, received little support among postdocs*. Just under two thirds of postdocs* (61.4 %) said they wanted to qualify for a professorship. Around one third (32 %) are pursuing the goal of being appointed to a permanent professorship within the next five years, while just under 29 % consider this a possible goal. In the 2nd JPS (Kauhaus et al., 2018), respondents were not asked about set goals but about the attractiveness of career goals. There, 54 % rated a university professorship as a very attractive or attractive career goal (p. 46).

Fig. 6.1: Career goals for the next five years (in %)

Note: Percentages are based on the number of valid cases in each category.

Mean comparisons show that the postdoc* sub-group express much stronger agreement with goals oriented towards an academic career than non-postdocs*, including completing a habilitation (postdocs*: $M = 2.11$, $SD = 0.88$, $n = 99$; non-postdocs*: $M = 1.56$, $SD = 0.74$, $n = 68$), qualifying for a professorship (postdocs*: $M = 2.17$, $SD = 0.89$, $n = 103$; non-postdocs*: $M = 1.67$, $SD = 0.79$, $n = 66$), making research more visible (postdocs*: $M = 2.66$, $SD = 0.63$, $n = 104$; non-postdocs*: $M = 2.23$, $SD = 0.85$, $n = 70$) and expanding academic network (postdocs*: $M = 2.69$, $SD = 0.64$, $n = 104$; non-postdocs*: $M = 2.41$, $SD = 0.83$, $n = 69$). In contrast, they less often pursue the goal of expanding their professional network outside academia (postdocs*: $M = 1.81$, $SD = 0.81$, $n = 102$; non-postdocs*: $M = 2.37$, $SD = 0.85$, $n = 67$).

Among the academic career goals, three goals are directly related to pursuing a professorship (hereafter referred to as professorship-oriented goals, this includes *completing a habilitation, qualifying for a professorship, being appointed to a permanent professorship*) and can be combined into a reliable subscale ($\alpha = .84$). Another item group combines research-related goals (*securing own third-party funding, making own research visible, expanding academic networks*; $\alpha = .79$). Due to small response numbers when considering multiple factors simultaneously, mean comparisons by gender, internationality and academic field are conducted separately. This analysis seems to have been worthwhile despite the small number of responses because the means numerically suggest no interaction between the factors.

For professorship-oriented goals, t-tests for gender and internationality show no significant differences between group means. Agreement with professorship-oriented goals does, however, differ significantly by research discipline ($F(2, 97) = 2.318, p = .012, \text{partial } \eta^2 = 0.09$). Post-hoc comparisons confirm that researchers in the humanities and social sciences ($M = 2.31, SD = 0.69$) pursue professorship-oriented goals more often than those in the natural sciences ($M = 1.88, SD = 0.76$). No significant group differences are evident for research-related goals.

Further interesting results emerge when the different position types aspired to are examined by time since doctorate completion. In the overall group, significant but weak associations ($\alpha < .05$; *Cramér's V* < .3) were found between time since doctorate and the goals of becoming a junior research group leader ($\chi^2(6, n = 159) = 16.54, p = .011, V = 0.23$), obtaining a junior professorship ($\chi^2(6, n = 167) = 16.42, p = .012, V = 0.22$) or taking up a position outside academia ($\chi^2(6, n = 168) = 17.67, p = .007, V = 0.23$). These effects are likely partly related to formal time requirements for certain career paths. For example, applications for junior professorships are possible in some federal states only up to four or six years after obtaining the doctorate (cf. § 30(5) NHG (*Lower Saxony Higher Education Act*); § 102a BerlHG (*Berlin Higher Education Act*)). Similarly, non-academic career goals are more frequently mentioned by people whose qualification period under the WissZeitVG is likely to end soon (see Fig. 6.2). Among the postdoc* sub-group, slightly stronger associations (*Cramér's V* > .3) were found with the goals of taking up a permanent position in academia ($\chi^2(2, n = 92) = 17.32, p = .008, V = 0.31$) and being appointed to a permanent professorship ($\chi^2(6, n = 100) = 18.10, p = .006, V = 0.30$). Agreement with both goals rose continuously with time since doctorate completion. It was highest among postdocs* whose doctorate was completed more than six years ago (permanent position: < 1 year, 38.5 % vs > 6 years, 74.2 %; permanent professorship: < 1 year, 7.1 % vs > 6 years, 56.8 %).

Fig. 6.2: Career goals by time since completion of the doctorate (in %)

Note: Percentages are based on the number of valid cases in each category.

For the dichotomised variable *educational pathway*, it was notable that people who had not studied, worked or completed their doctorate at the University of Münster before commencing their current postdoc position were more likely to affirm goals related to a long-term academic career (see Fig. 6.3). This was particularly clear for the goals of meeting professorship qualification criteria ($\chi^2(2, n = 169) = 9.10, p = .011, V = 0.23$; postdocs*: $\chi^2(2, n = 103) = 8.51, p = .014, V = 0.29$) and being appointed to a permanent professorship ($\chi^2(2, n = 166) = 9.65, p = .008, V = 0.24$). This suggests that researchers who remain at the University of Münster after their doctorate or return there tend to pursue career goals other than a professorship. Also, researchers with a professorship career goal show greater geographical flexibility and more frequently move between universities.

Fig. 6.3: Career goals by educational pathway (in %)

Note: Percentages are based on the number of valid cases in each category.

At the end of this question block, participants were asked how CERes, as the central graduate centre, could support them in planning their professional future. The free-text responses were evaluated using content analysis and grouped through inductive category formation (Mayring, 2010). In particular, mention was made of the need for greater visibility of services, individual advice, information on the academic system and alternative career paths, the desire for (peer-)mentoring programmes and training offers on various topics. It was repeatedly emphasised that it was not a lack of information or poor career planning, but the limited opportunities in the German academic system, that posed the central challenge. At the same time, satisfaction with existing services was expressed, for example, in this comment:

Die Angebote und Unterstützung, die es an der Uni Münster, sowohl zentral als auch an meinem Fachbereich gibt, finde ich bereits umfangreich und auf jeden Fall sehr hilfreich. Ich möchte an dieser Stelle also ein Lob aussprechen und hoffe, dass die Angebote in ihrer jetzigen Form beibehalten werden.

[The offers and support available at the University of Münster, both centrally and in my faculty, I already find comprehensive and certainly very helpful. I therefore want to express my praise at this point and hope that the offers are maintained in their current form.]

7 Training Needs and Offers

To achieve their career goals, further development of transferable skills is as important as subject-specific and didactic abilities. At CERes, a category system was developed based on the competence models of UniWinD, EU ResearchComp and Vitae UK, encompassing the following cross-disciplinary qualification areas: *discipline-specific competences*, *academic professionalism*, *techniques of academic work*, *self-management*, *research management*, *teaching and didactics*, and *social responsibility and knowledge transfer*.¹⁹ At the start of this question block, respondents were asked about their training needs in these areas. The items demonstrated good internal reliability ($\alpha = .81$), so they were also combined into an overall variable, *training needs (overall)*. The mean comparison (see Table 7.1: Statistical comparison of training needs) shows that our respondents report a moderate overall need for further training. The need is comparatively high in *research management*, *teaching and didactics*, as well as in *social responsibility and knowledge transfer*, and lowest in techniques of academic work. Among postdocs*, the pattern is similar. Only in the area of subject-related competences is the mean noticeably higher ($M = 2.75$, $SD = 1$, $n = 107$).

Table 7.1: Statistical comparison of training needs

Item	<i>n</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	α
Training needs (overall)	191	2.91	0.73	0.81
Discipline-specific competences	186	2.65	1	
Academic professionalism	186	2.74	1	
Techniques of academic work	186	2.52	1	
Self-management	186	2.91	1.10	
Research management	186	3.35	1.10	
Teaching and didactics	186	3.17	1.10	
Social responsibility and transfer	186	3.14	1.10	

Note: *n* = sample size, *M* = mean, *SD* = standard deviation, α = Cronbach's Alpha

In a free-text field, respondents were asked to name the institutions and programmes known to them for further training at the University of Münster. The responses mention, almost exclusively, central institutions, departments and programmes: faculty-specific offers were rarely

¹⁹ The qualification areas of discipline-specific competences and teaching and didactics were included for completeness, but do not form part of CERes's remit. The specific skills belonging to each area can be found in the questionnaire in the Appendix.

named. The most frequently mentioned services were the *personnel development department*, the *Centre for Higher Education Teaching*, the *Münster Centre for Emerging Researchers* and *Research Funding Support (SAFIR)*. Eight people said they knew of no further training opportunities.

Participants were also asked, via a matrix listing specific further training offerings and topics, which offerings would support or had supported them in achieving their long-term goals after the doctorate. As the agreement values (response = *yes*) in Fig. 7.1: Agreement values for further training offers (in %) show, respondents rated offerings related to third-party funding applications, individual career coaching, leadership training and project management as particularly helpful. These findings reflect the comparatively high mean training need in research management (see Table 6.1).

Fig. 7.1: Agreement values for further training offers (in %)

Note: Only offers rated as helpful by more than half of respondents are shown. Percentages are based on the number of valid cases in each category.

Chi-square analyses revealed several significant associations, for example, between *research disciplines* and the offerings *writing retreat* ($\chi^2(2, n = 164) = 7.65, p = .020, V = 0.22$) and *exchange with representatives from business, industry and politics* ($\chi^2(1, n = 168) = 10.51, p = .005, V = 0.25$). Writing retreats were most frequently rated as helpful by postdocs from the humanities and social sciences (55.9 %), more so than in the life sciences (39.3 %) or natural sciences (32.5 %). Conversely, respondents from the natural (67.9 %) and life sciences (62.1 %) were more likely to rate

extra-university networking offerings as helpful than those from the humanities and social sciences (41 %).

Statistical effects were also evident for some further training offers depending on *internationality*. These were particularly strong for *language courses* ($\chi^2(1, n = 168) = 28.81, p < .001, V = 0.41$) and *introduction to the German academic system* ($\chi^2(1, n = 169) = 12.54, p < .001, V = 0.27$). This aligns with the findings of the InWiDeHo study (2023), which states that needs-based German courses and transparent information on career paths in the German academic system are particularly important for removing barriers to academic careers for international researchers in Germany (p. 126).

Finally, medium to strong gender-specific effects were found for *project management* ($\chi^2(1, n = 181) = 6.50, p = .010, V = 0.19$) and individual career coaching ($\chi^2(1, n = 171) = 20.10, p < .001, V = 0.34$). Individual career coaching stands out in particular: while 61.8 % of male respondents rated it as helpful, 90.5 % of female respondents did so. This underscores the importance of personal support in the career development of female postdocs in particular.

Respondents were then asked, in a matrix using a five-point scale, which factors increased or decreased the likelihood they would participate in further training offers. Positive values indicate an increase and negative values a reduction in the likelihood of participation. The means (see Table 7.2) show that time-related factors have the greatest influence on the likelihood of participation. Scheduling events during the lecture period slightly reduces the likelihood of participation, while one-off or half-day sessions markedly increase it. For international postdocs, the likelihood rises significantly if offerings are held in English ($t(173) = -12.23, p < .001, d = 0.20$).

Table 7.2: Statistical comparison of the likelihood of participation

Item	<i>n</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
During lecture period (rather than outside)	173	-0.34	1
In English (rather than in German)	175	0.19	0.90
In person (rather than via Zoom)	176	-0.03	1.14
As e-learning (rather than instructor-led)	171	-0.04	1.21
Half-day (rather than full-day)	174	0.96	0.92
One-off session (rather than course series)	169	0.94	0.73
During regular working hours (rather than evenings)	175	0.76	1.12
With childcare (rather than without)	160	0.36	0.77
For interdisciplinary group (rather than discipline-specific)	167	0.10	0.77
Only with postdocs (rather than also with doctoral researchers)	169	0.63	0.74

Note: *n* = sample size, *M* = mean, *SD* = standard deviation

In the free-text fields, some respondents provided additional comments on factors influencing the likelihood they would participate. Through inductive category formation, *time-related*, *content-related* and *formal factors* were identified. Among the factors that promote participation were certificate issuance, recognition of training time as working time, and early and repeated announcements of dates. Content-wise, offers for advanced postdocs and in-depth advice following training increased the likelihood of participation. Time-related factors yielded partly contradictory assessments: some postdocs preferred morning or early afternoon sessions, particularly in connection with childcare, while others found exactly the same times obstructive.

The closing comments at the end of the survey provided supplementary insight. Alongside general thanks and appreciation for the survey, three themes were repeatedly highlighted: *diversity*, *systemic challenges* and *visibility*. The statements illustrate the diversity of biographies among those identifying as postdocs and emphasise the need to accommodate this diversity in support offers. A few respondents also pointed to structural limitations of the German academic system that cannot be offset by training or advisory formats alone:

Ich schätze den Ansatz des CERes prinzipiell und es ist natürlich besser, dass es die Angebote zur Vernetzung, Information und Fortbildung gibt. Hilft alles leider nur begrenzt, solange die wissenschaftliche Karriere letztlich nur das Motto ‚up or out‘ kennt.

[I fundamentally appreciate CERes's approach, and it is of course better that networking, information and training offers exist. Unfortunately, this only helps to a limited extent as long as academic careers ultimately follow the motto "up or out".]

The comments on visibility show, on the one hand, that offerings need to better reach the target group, which the survey itself evidently achieved: "Before this survey notification, I didn't even know CERes existed." ("Vor dieser Benachrichtigung zur Umfrage wusste ich nicht, dass es das CERes überhaupt gibt"). On the other hand, it is repeatedly noted that the survey positively contributed to the visibility of the postdoc group, as this comment illustrates:

Vielen Dank für diese Umfrage! Ich habe seit langem endlich das Gefühl, dass ein gewisses Interesse daran besteht, wie es Personen ohne Professur geht. Ich hoffe, Sie erreichen damit noch viel mehr Post-Docs und ich bin sehr an den Ergebnissen interessiert.

[Thank you very much for this survey! For the first time in a long while, I finally have the feeling that there is some interest in how people without professorships are doing. I hope you reach many more postdocs with this, and I am very interested in the results.]

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Appendix

Free-text Responses: Satisfaction and Dissatisfaction Aspects

This table shows the results of a qualitative analysis of free-text responses about which aspects of the work situation the survey respondents are satisfied or dissatisfied with. Since the burden and well-being factors overlap substantially with the satisfaction responses, the presentation is limited to aspects of (dis)satisfaction. Although the most frequent and substantively important responses are listed, the frequencies of individual statements cannot be read from the table, as repetitions have been omitted. Unedited, longer anchor examples are shown in *italics* and, for better readability, are alternately formatted in black and green.

Table 0.1: Satisfaction and dissatisfaction aspects of postdocs (categorised)

	Aspects of satisfaction		Aspects of dissatisfaction	
Freedom	Flexibility Work-life balance Little control	Generally	Dependence on supervisors Personal feeling of overload Control	
	Flexible working hours Free scheduling of working hours Family-friendly working hours Possibility to offer block courses	Time-related	Future	Unclear prospects Lack of predictability/stability Career uncertainty
			Working hours	Compatibility of family and work Compatibility of research and training Excessive workload (even in part-time employment) Trust-based working hours

	Flexibility of workplace Remote work	Spatial	Commuting Family and social life – not easily compatible with frequent moves
	Freedom to set topics/foci in research and teaching Individual design of experiments Budget responsibility	Content/structural	Too many administrative tasks Unclear job profiles Pressure to work, apply, present and publish Little room for own projects Faculty's lack of interest in interdisciplinary teaching (only for interdisciplinary research within funded projects)
Meaningfulness	Fulfilling activity Ability to work on exciting topics Enthusiasm for the research field Feeling of being able to make a difference Support students and PhDs in their research and help them further. Ich liebe Forschung und Lehre. (I love research and teaching.) I am satisfied about the intellectual challenges. I love science. If I would not love science, I would have left years ago.		

<p style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">Appreciation</p>	<p>Through the discipline-specific academic community From colleagues and students Work group Supervisor</p>		<p>Lack of appreciation for teaching within the academic community Little appreciation for holders of permanent positions</p> <p><i>Ich bin mit einer veröffentlichten Doktorarbeit und einer ausgezeichneten Promotion hierhergekommen, doch ich habe das Gefühl, dass meine Beiträge und die Mühe, die ich in das Projekt stecke, weder ausreichend wertgeschätzt noch wahrgenommen werden.</i></p> <p>(I came here with a published doctoral thesis and an outstanding doctorate, but I feel that my contributions and the effort I put into the project are neither sufficiently appreciated nor noticed.)</p> <p><i>I also do quite some extra unpaid work for my institute (organizing events, Gremienarbeit) and I do not feel that this is appreciated.</i></p>
<p style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">Collaboration</p>	<p><i>Die Beziehung zu meinem Vorgesetzten schätze ich sehr, von ihm bin nicht überlastet und bekomme Unterstützung und Anerkennung.</i></p> <p>(I greatly value my relationship with my supervisor; I am not overloaded by them and receive support and recognition.)</p>	<p>With supervisor(s)</p>	<p>Partly intrusive supervisor behaviour</p> <p><i>Professor*innen planen immer mehr die Daumenschrauben für den Nachwuchs anzuziehen. Sie selbst sind ja Professor*innen, üben ihre Macht aus und müssen sich keine Sorgen mehr machen.</i></p> <p>(Professors are increasingly planning to tighten the screws on early-career researchers. They themselves are professors, exercise their power and no longer have to worry.)</p> <p><i>Beziehung zu Vorgesetztem ist äußerst schwierig (keine Unterstützung für eigene Karriere, legt mir Hindernisse in den Weg, unzuverlässig, nimmt schon gemachte Zusagen z.B. zu Budget wieder zurück, äußerst launisch...): das hat leider große Auswirkungen auf alles andere, auch wenn meine Beziehung zu allen anderen KollegInnen und meinen Post-docs und Promovierenden ansonsten sehr gut ist.</i></p> <p>(Relationship with supervisor is extremely difficult (no support for my own career, puts obstacles in my way, unreliable, withdraws already made promises, e.g., on budget, extremely moody...): this unfortunately has major effects on everything else, even though my</p>

			<p>relationship with all other colleagues, my postdocs and doctoral researchers is otherwise very good.)</p> <p><i>Engagement des Chefs, mich karrieretechnisch weiterzubringen (hat oft keine Zeit, um etwas zu lesen...)</i></p> <p>(Supervisor's commitment to advancing my career (often has no time to read anything...))</p>
	<p>Social environment</p> <p>Sensational colleagues</p> <p>Great team atmosphere</p> <p>Being allowed to work with very smart and motivated people</p>	<p>in the faculty/with students</p>	<p>Some contacts with researchers in Münster</p> <p>Great colleagues who are retiring :-((</p> <p>A certain degree of unprofessionalism among team members</p>
	<p>Contacts with researchers nationally and internationally</p> <p>Involvement in teaching</p> <p><i>My direct working group is quite good and I feel secure there and that I can ask questions, try things etc.</i></p> <p><i>I can often go to international conferences.</i></p>	<p>Support/ communication</p>	<p><i>It is hard to negotiate and develop within the academic hierarchy. The position I have is technically quite prestigious [name of position] but I do not have a clear place in the institute or research group hierarchy, nor the freedom to build a fully independent platform, and my career progression honestly feels like it has stalled.</i></p> <p><i>I am unhappy with [...] the fact that international colleagues are often excluded from social as well as scholarly events because of the use of German (I do speak German fluently, so this is not a problem for me, but there is a lack of a welcoming atmosphere for non-German-speaking colleagues).</i></p>
<p>Structures</p>	<p>Good workplace equipment</p> <p>High quality of library(ies)</p>	<p>Infrastructure</p>	<p>Nature of workplace</p> <p>Very little support and budget at the University of Münster for developing one's own career (within or outside academia)</p> <p>Lack of personnel concept at the institute</p> <p>Lack of substitution rules</p> <p>Publication landscape</p> <p>Canteen (especially price-performance ratio)</p>

	<p>Current scholarship for a research stay abroad</p>	<p>Salary</p>	<p>Working at the weekend without receiving additional pay</p> <p><i>Momentanes Gehalt und Gehaltsperspektiven für jemanden mit Promotion und Berufserfahrung. Gerade auch im Vergleich zu anderen Berufen mit Promotion.</i></p> <p>(Current salary and salary prospects for someone with a doctorate and professional experience, particularly in comparison with other professions requiring a doctorate.)</p> <p><i>I am unhappy with the fact that I carry out unpaid teaching work.</i></p>
	<p>Permanent employment contract</p>	<p>Employment contract</p>	<p>Fixed-term employment contract Number of permanent positions Fear of the WissZeitVG</p> <p><i>Das Einzige, was mich schmerzt, ist die ständige Befristung und die Unsicherheit, ob der nächste Drittmittelantrag, an dem die eigene Existenz hängt, bewilligt wird (und auch rechtzeitig!). Mein größter Wunsch ist eine Dauerstelle zur Forschung!</i></p> <p>(The only thing that hurts me is the constant fixed-term contracts and the uncertainty whether the next third-party funding application, on which my existence depends, will be approved (and on time!). My greatest wish is a permanent position for research!)</p> <p><i>Es gibt den Beruf [Nennung des Fachs] Wissenschaftler im Prinzip nicht. Wenn man also Wissenschaftler ist, der forschen möchte, aber nicht habilitieren, landet man früher oder später außerhalb der Uni/Forschung in einem anderen Job. Da helfen leider auch keine Karriereplanungen. Ich bin in meiner Karriere genau da, wo ich sein möchte, darf aber leider nicht bleiben. Entweder Habilitation oder Ende...</i></p>

(There is basically no job as a [mention of subject] researcher. So, if you want to do research as a researcher but not habilitate, you end up sooner or later outside the university/research in another job. Unfortunately, no career planning can help with that. I am exactly where I want to be in my career, but unfortunately, I am not allowed to stay. Either habilitation or end...)

Ich muss pendeln, weil ich Familie habe und für einen 3-Jahresvertrag nicht umziehe. Es ist nicht planbar oder absehbar, ob ich im Umfeld meines Wohnorts eine Stelle erhalte, dabei habe ich mich hoch qualifiziert. [...] Hätte ich keinen Partner, der die Unsicherheit (ökonomisch und sozial) abfedert, wäre es für mich als Mutter nicht möglich als Postdoc zu arbeiten.

(I have to commute because I have a family and won't move for a 3-year contract. It is not predictable or foreseeable whether I will get a position near my place of residence, even though I have highly qualified myself. [...] If I didn't have a partner who cushions the uncertainty (financially and socially), it would not be possible for me as a mother to work as a postdoc.)

Questionnaire

A. Academic Vita and Working Situation

Let's start with a few questions about the general conditions of your academic working life. Your answers will help us to get a better overview of postdocs in Münster and to identify the specific needs of different target groups in the evaluation.

1. How many years ago did you obtain your doctorate?

The date of the defence applies.

- a. < 1 year
- b. 1–3 years
- c. 4–6 years
- d. > 6 years
- e. No answer

2. Which scientific discipline do you belong to?

In order to reduce the identifiability of individuals, we follow the [subject classification system of the German Research Foundation](#) (DFG) instead of using the faculty classification of the University of Münster.

- a. Humanities and Social Sciences
- b. Life Sciences
- c. Natural Sciences
- d. Engineering Sciences
- e. Other
- f. No answer

3. Which stages of your academic qualification did you complete at the University of Münster?

	Yes	No	No answer
I studied (temporarily) at the University of Münster.			
I completed my doctorate at the University of Münster.			
I obtained a postdoctoral position at the University of Münster directly following my doctorate.			

4. What is your current job title at the University of Münster?

- a. Research associate (Wissenschaftliche*r Mitarbeiter*in)
- b. Junior research group leader or junior professor
- c. Other academic job title (e.g. lecturer (*Akademische*r Rät*in*), university instructor with high teaching load (*Studienrät*in* or *Lehrkraft für besondere Aufgaben*))
- d. Non-academic staff
- e. Other
- f. No answer

5. Please select all conditions that apply to your current employment relationship.

The percentages refer to the proportion of regular weekly working hours.

As employment relationships can consist of different contracts with different conditions, you have the option of selecting several answers here.

- a. Temporary position \leq 65 %
- b. Temporary position 66–99 %
- c. Temporary position 100 %
- d. Permanent position \leq 65 %
- e. Permanent position 66–99 %
- f. Permanent position 100 %
- g. No answer

6. Does your employment contract include a teaching obligation?

- a. Yes
- b. No
- c. No answer

[Condition: "Yes"]:

6a. What is the extent of your teaching obligation?

- a. < 5 hours of instruction per week
- b. 5–10 hours of instruction per week
- c. > 10 hours of instruction per week
- d. No answer

[Condition: "No"]:

6b. Which of the following scenarios applies to your situation?

- a. I do not teach.
- b. I do not teach but I would like to teach.
- c. I teach anyway.
- d. No answer

7. How is your position financed?

You can select multiple answers.

- a. University or faculty budget
- b. Third-party funds
- c. Scholarship
- d. Other
- e. I don't know.
- f. No answer

8. Approximately what percentage of your weekly working time do you spend on the following tasks during an average working week?

Please use numbers between 1-100 (no '%') and **make sure the sum does not exceed 100**.

If a task area does not apply to your work situation, please enter 0. If you do not wish to answer, please leave the corresponding field blank.

	During the lecture period	Outside the lecture period	Does not apply	No answer
Research & work on your own topic (reading, research, experiments, analyses, conference participation, publishing, peer review, etc.)				
Teaching (incl. preparation, follow-up, supervising and examining students & doctoral researchers, etc.)				
Administrative tasks & management (data management, accounting, formal application for third-party funding, organising own events, science communication, study programme coordination, etc.)				
Tasks for your supervisor (grading exams, preparing publications, organising events, etc.)				
Training (subject-specific and overarching workshops, trainings, courses, certificates, etc.)				
Committee work & networking (at the University of Münster, in research societies or networks, etc.)				

8a. Would you like to add any further tasks?

- Ja
- Nein
- Keine Antwort

[Condition: "Yes"]:

8b. As above, please enter the approximate percentage of your weekly working time that you spend on these additional activities during an average working week and **make sure that the total of 100 is not exceeded by any additional activity(ies)**.

	Name of the task	During the lecture period	Outside the lecture period
Additional activity 1			
Additional activity 2			
Additional activity 3			

9. If you now think of an ideal time distribution of your tasks: How do you estimate your average time expenditure for the respective area of activity in comparison?

If you do not wish to answer or a task area does not apply to your work situation, please select 'No answer' at the appropriate point.

	Much too high	Rather too high	Just right	Rather low	Much too low	No answer
Research & work on your own topic (reading, research, experiments, analyses, conference participation, publishing, peer review, etc.)						
Teaching (preparation, follow-up, supervising and examining students & doctoral researchers, etc.)						
Administrative tasks & management (data management, accounting, formal application for third-party funding, organising own events, science communication, study programme coordination, etc.)						
Tasks for your supervisor (grading exams, preparing publications, organising events, etc.)						
Training (subject-specific and overarching workshops, trainings, courses, certificates, etc.)						
Committee work & networking (at the University of Münster, in research societies or networks, etc.)						
Additional activity 1						
Additional activity 2						
Additional activity 3						

10. How strongly do you identify yourself with the following terms?

	Not at all	Rather not	Neutral	Rather strongly	Very strongly	No answer
Early career researcher						
Emerging researcher						
Junior Researcher						
Scientist / researcher						
Postdoc / postdoctoral researcher						
Subject-specific term, e.g. Biologist, Mathematician, Psychologist etc.						

10a. Other work-related terms with which you identify:

B. Demographics

This information is crucial for evaluating the survey as well as for analysing the needs and conditions of specific target groups.

1. Which gender do you identify with?

- a. Female
- b. Male
- c. Diverse
- d. Other
- e. None
- f. No answer

2. How old are you?

- a. < 30 years
- b. 30–35 years
- c. 36–40 years
- d. > 40 years
- e. No answer

3. Where did you spend most of the following educational phases?

	In Germany	Within a European country except Germany	Within a non-European country	No answer
School				
College				
Doctoral phase				
Time after the doctorate				

4. For how long do you plan to stay in Germany?

- a. <1 year
- b. 1–3 years
- c. 4–6 years
- d. >6 years
- e. No answer

5. Which language do you **mainly** speak in your **professional** environment?

- a. German
- b. English
- c. Another language
- d. No answer

6. Which language do you **mainly** speak in your **family** environment?

- a. German
- b. English
- c. Another language
- d. No answer

7. Approximately how much time per week do you spend on the following activities?

	< 5 hours	5–10 hours	11–15 hours	> 15 hours	Does not apply	No answer
Care work						
Secondary occupation / self-employed work						
Volunteer work / Political involvement						
Other						

[Condition: “< 5 hours”, “5–10 hours”, “11–15 hours” or “> 15 hours” for “Other”]:

7a. Those other activities include:

8. Which scenarios apply to your educational biography?

	Yes	No	No answer
I am the first person in my immediate origin family (parents, siblings) to have obtained a university degree (BA/MA/Diploma).			
I am the first person I am the first person in my immediate origin family (parents, siblings) to have obtained a doctoral degree.			
I am the first person in my extended origin family (grandparents, aunts, uncles, cousins) to have obtained a doctoral degree.			
At least one person in my immediate or extended origin family is a professor at university or a similar institution.			
Before I started my doctorate, I already knew a few people from my family or friends who pursued a career in academia.			
My partner also works in academia.			

C. Job Satisfaction and Occupational Stress Experience

In this section, we would like to know more about your level of satisfaction and stress at work. Your answers will help us to better understand the work situation of postdocs in Münster and to be sensitised to this in our counselling and training offers in order to support you within the scope of our possibilities.

We start with five questions about your job satisfaction. These concern aspects of collaboration and networking, general working conditions and your overall satisfaction.

1. To what extent do you agree with the following statements on **collaboration and networking** with other people in your day-to-day work?

	I strongly disagree	No answer				
I experience the cooperation with my direct colleagues as successful.						
I experience appreciation for my work in the workplace and in the professional community.						
I receive good feedback and support from my supervisor(s).						
I have a good network with researchers from other working groups.						
I have a lot of contact with researchers in a similar career phase.						
I experience a feeling of security and trust in my social working environment.						

2. How satisfied are you with the following **general working conditions**?

	Very dissatisfied	Rather dissatisfied	Rather satisfied	Very satisfied	Does not apply	No answer
Degree of independence						
Availability of funding for own research						
Scope and length of working hours						
Fixed-term duration of your contract						
Act on Fixed-Term Employment Contracts in Academia (WissZeitVG*) *This law regulates the fixed-term employment of academic						

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staff in Germany, stipulating the conditions for and limits to such it.						
Career advancement opportunities						
Opportunities for professional reorientation						
Career predictability						
Social relationships in the work context						
Family-friendly environment						
Time for your private life						

2a. Other **general working conditions** that you are **satisfied** with or comments on those conditions:

2b. Other **general working conditions** that you are **dissatisfied** with or comments on those conditions:

3. All in all, how satisfied are you with your current work situation?

- a. Very dissatisfied
- b. Rather dissatisfied
- c. Rather satisfied
- d. Very satisfied
- e. No answer

[Condition: "very dissatisfied" or "rather dissatisfied"]:

3a. What would help to increase your overall satisfaction?

Now we would like to know more about the potential stress you experience at work, the sources of this stress and how you cope with it. Your answers will help us to get a clearer picture of the work-related well-being of postdocs in Münster and to identify possible support measures.

4. How often do you feel overly stressed* at work?

**Overly stressed meaning that the stress you experience noticeably affects your well-being.*

- a. (Almost) Never
- b. A few times per year
- c. (Almost) Once a month
- d. At least once a week
- e. Several times per week
- f. (Almost) Daily
- g. No answer

5. Which aspects of your working life (e.g. work tasks, working conditions, social working environment) are particularly stressful for you?

6. Which aspects of your working life (e.g. work tasks, working conditions, social working environment, etc.) contribute to your well-being?

7. Who do you talk to about your work-related stress?

	Yes	No	No answer
Supervisor(s)			
Colleague(s)			
Partner and/or family			
Friend(s)			
Counsellor(s) at the University of Münster			
Professional contact(s): General practitioner, psychologist, psychotherapist			
No one			

Other

8. Please enter here which other groups of people you talk to about your work-related stress:

9. Which services and contact points at the University of Münster do you know that can help you cope with stress/strain or that can support you in increasing your level of well-being?

10. What ideas do you have about how CERes as a central graduate institution could support you in coping with stress or increasing your well-being?

D. Career Planning and Prospects

Next, we will ask you questions about your plans and planning strategies for your future career. Your answers will help us to better tailor our career development counselling and events to your needs.

1. How good do you think is your knowledge about the **German academic system**, i.e. the organisational structure of universities, career options, qualification requirements, research culture, funding opportunities, etc.?

Very poor	Rather poor	Rather good	Very good	No answer

[Condition: "very poor" or "rather poor"]:

1a. You answered that your knowledge of the German academic system is very or rather poor. **What aspects or topics would you like to be better informed about?**

2. How good do you think is your knowledge about the **academic systems in other countries**

Very poor	Rather poor	Rather good	Very good	No answer

[Condition: "very poor" or "rather poor"]:

2a. You answered that your knowledge of the academic systems in other countries is very or rather poor. **What aspects or topics would you like to be better informed about? Are there specific countries whose systems you would like to know more about?**

3. Which points of contact at the University of Münster do you know that can help you with planning your career or gather information about career options and prospects?

--

4. The following items are about your career plans. Please indicate the extent to which you agree with each statement.

	I completely disagree.	I rather disagree.	I rather agree.	I completely agree.	No answer
I know exactly what I want to achieve in the next 5 years.					
I know exactly which steps I need to take to achieve my 5-year-goal(s).					
I intend to obtain further qualifications in my current field of employment.					
I intend to obtain further qualifications in a different field of employment.					
I feel positive about my job prospects within academia.					
I feel positive about my job prospects outside academia.					

5. What are your specific goals for the next 5 years?

	Yes	Maybe	No	No answer
Finish my habilitation <i>(Habilitation is an academic degree in Germany that is frequently required to qualify for a professorship.)</i>				
Fulfil the qualification criteria for a professorship				
Acquire my own third-party funding				
A higher visibility of my research (in my research community or in public)				
Go on a research stay abroad				
Broaden my professional academic network				
Broaden my professional non-academic network				
Acquire a permanent position in university academia				
Work in a leadership position				

Become junior research group leader				
Be appointed to a junior professorship (with/without tenure track)				
Be appointed to a lifetime professorship				
Work in science management				
Find a position outside of university academia				
Start a business				
Other				

[Condition: „Yes“ or „Maybe“ for „Other“]:

5a. Please name further goals here:

6. How often have you talked to someone in your work environment (e.g. supervisor, colleague, counselling services) specifically about planning your professional future **since your doctorate**?
- a. More often than once a semester
 - b. Once a semester
 - c. Once a year
 - d. Less than once a year
 - e. Not at all
 - f. No answer

7. How can CERes as a central graduate centre best support you in planning your professional future?

E. Further Training Needs

The following information about your needs for professional development are particularly important for the design and adaptation of our training and events programme for postdocs.

1. How would you rate the extent of your **need for further training** in the following areas?

	Very low	Rather low	Moderate	Rather high	Very high	No answer
Discipline-specific competencies (discipline-specific content knowledge and skills, research methodology knowledge and skills, information management, communication (written and spoken), values and rules)						
Academic professionalism (social relationships in the scientific community; ethics, values, norms, and rules in academic research; Open Science)						
Techniques of academic work (information management; reading, writing and presenting; creativity techniques; logic and analysis)						
Self-management (health and well-being; motivation; individual career development)						
Management (time and project management; teamwork and leadership; generation of financial resources)						
Teaching and didactics (teaching and learning; testing and grading; feedback and evaluation; advising; innovative teaching)						
Social responsibility & transfer (science communication; knowledge transfer and practical application of research results)						

1a. In which other areas not covered here do you see a need for further training?

2. Which institutions and services at the University of Münster do you know that can help you train and expand your skills and competencies?

3. Which generic courses and offers on the following topics would help you or (would) have previously helped you to achieve your long term goals **after** your doctorate?

	Yes	No	No answer
Introduction to the German academic system			
Academic writing in a foreign language			
Writing retreat			
Data analysis			
Project management			
Grant application writing / strategic third-party funding coaching			
Professional networking			
Job application training (job search, application writing, job interview)			
Leadership training			
Anti-procrastination and motivation training			
Communication and presentation skills			
Language courses (incl. German as a foreign language)			
Individual career coaching			
Career-oriented peer coaching			
Exchange with representatives from business, industry, politics, etc.			
Networking and social events			
Other			

[Condition: „Yes“ for „Other“]:

3a. Please enter further generic courses that have helped or would have helped you to achieve your professional goals **after** your doctorate:

4. As a central scientific centre, CERes provides overarching services for researchers, such as workshops, counselling and networking events. We would like to know:

	Have you used the following offers so far?		Will you use the following services in the future?			No answer
	Yes	No	Yes	No	Maybe	
Workshops on overarching topics						
Information on the website						
Individual counselling / coaching						
Writing meet-ups/retreats						
Networking / social events						

- 4a. Other offers I would like CERes to provide and that I would use:

5. We at CERes endeavour to tailor our services to your needs: Which factors decrease or increase the probability of you participating in our events and using our services?

The offer/event takes place...	Greatly decreases probability of use	Slightly decreases probability of use	Has no influence	Slightly increases probability of use	Greatly increases probability of use	No answer
during the lecture period (instead of during the lecture-free period).						
in English (instead of in German).						
in presence (instead of via Zoom).						
as an e-learning / autodidactic offer (instead of with a trainer).						
over half a day (instead of over a full day).						
as a one-off event (instead of a series of events).						
during regular working hours (instead of in the evening).						

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with childcare (instead of without child care).						
with participants from different disciplines (instead of discipline-specific).						
only among post-docs (instead of also with doctoral researchers)						

5a. Other factors that **decrease** the probability of you using the services at CERes:

5b. Other factors that **increase** the probability of you using the services at CERes:

6. What are good ways to reach and inform you about postdoc-specific news, topics and events at CERes and beyond?

	Yes	No	No answer
Postdoc Mattermost channel			
University-wide mailing list for postdocs			
Monthly postdoc newsletter			
E-mail via your faculty / research institution			
Digital or in person meetings once a semester for all postdocs			
Posters or displays near my office			
I don't want to be reached or informed.			
Other			

[Condition: „Yes“ for „Other“]:

6a. Please enter the other channels here:

7. From your perspective as a postdoc, what else would you like to pass on to CERes regarding the topics covered in the survey up to this point?

You have answered the last questions of this survey.

If you have any comments, questions or feedback for us, please leave it in the box below:

[Randomisation: „Group 1“]:

You have answered the last question of the regular questionnaire. Do you have **5 more minutes** to answer some additional questions about **job satisfaction and occupational stress experience**? Your participation would help us to get a clearer picture of the working situation of postdocs in Münster.

- a. Yes
- b. No
- c. No answer

[Condition: „Yes“ → Show additional category D]:

You have now reached the final supplementary question. Thank you very much for your time!

If you have any comments, questions or feedback for us, please use the text box below:

[Condition: „No“ oder „No answer“ → Completion of survey]

If you have any comments, questions or feedback for us, please use the text box below:

[Randomisation: „Group 2“]:

You have answered the last question of the regular questionnaire. Do you have **5 more minutes** to answer some additional questions about **career planning and prospects**? Your participation would help us to get a clearer picture of the working situation of postdocs in Münster.

- a. Yes
- b. No
- c. No answer

[Condition: „Yes“ → Show additional category C]:

You have now reached the final supplementary question. Thank you very much for your time!

If you have any comments, questions or feedback for us, please use the text box below:

[Condition: „No“ or „No answer“ → Completion of survey]

If you have any comments, questions or feedback for us, please use the text box below: